

D3.2 Final Report: Communities and Usage of Services

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Deliverable Abstract:

The European Open Science Cloud (EOOSC)-Pillar National Initiatives Survey (NIS) (Bodlos et al., 2020) provides insights into the landscape of the research supporting infrastructure in the five EOOSC-Pillar countries (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, and Italy). Following the NIS dedicated to research supporting infrastructures, Work Package 3 additionally carried out qualitative interviews and a quantitative survey dedicated to user communities. This deliverable outlines three main contributions. First, we disseminated and discussed the NIS results with open science experts. Second, we conducted qualitative interviews with 14 researchers about their data reuse behavior. Third, we carried out a quantitative survey with researchers in five different countries about their data reuse behavior.

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Executive summary

This deliverable focuses on the dissemination activities of the NIS and additional results and recommendations derived from a survey on user communities (researchers). First, we discuss the results gained through the dissemination of the National Initiatives Survey. [Chapter 1](#) lists the organized events. [Chapter 2](#) outlines the literature on data reuse and identifies its gaps. Third, we conducted qualitative interviews with 14 researchers about their data reuse behavior in [Chapter 3](#). Finally, in [Chapter 4](#) we carried out a quantitative survey with researchers from 5 different countries about their reuse behavior. The qualitative questionnaire contained questions based on principles concerning challenges and issues related to the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data (FAIR) across disciplines. The quantitative survey questionnaire addressed data reuse, reusability, and attitudes and behavior. The following table summarizes the key findings of each section.

NIS Dissemination Events	Main recommendations
The role of policies	Improve of communication between stakeholders Increase researcher motivation and support
Health and Biodiversity	Increase training (in local languages)
FAIR data	Focus on strategy at the technical and policy level
Motivations and Obstacles	Provide mesocenters staff with better knowledge of EOSC
Webinar Event in Germany	Maintain and improve communication methods
Mini-hackathon	Organize hackathons to foster data reuse
Qualitative Interviews	Main recommendations
	Provide one-point entries and less bureaucratic hurdles Increase automatization for data findability Improve standardized vocabularies and metadata quality
Quantitative Survey	Main recommendations
	Encourage the use of data papers as an incentive Create researcher networks to spread knowledge of EOSC

Introduction

The Horizon 2020 (H2020) EOSC-Pillar project conducted the NIS among universities, funding bodies, research infrastructures and e-infrastructures in five European countries (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, and Italy). The survey provided a landscape of research data and services as it relates to EOSC ([survey results available here](#)). One of the main goals and purposes of the H2020 project (defined in the grant agreement and suggested by the mid-term review) was to disseminate the results in order to derive recommendations and receive continuous input on the project. Another goal was to focus on user communities (researchers) in order to understand their perspectives.

To this end, we followed a three-tiered approach detailed in this deliverable. First, we presented the results of the NIS in webinars open for everyone and workshops for smaller thematic groups in [Chapter 1](#). The aim was to spark discussion among participants and answer the following questions: *How did participants interpret the results? What recommendations can be derived?* These events fulfilled the goals of monitoring and dissemination over the entire period defined in the grant agreement. [Chapter 2](#) covers the literature regarding data reuse and identifies the research gap. Third, to fulfill our goal of suggesting recommendations based on the perspective and wishes of researchers, we carried out in-depth interviews with 14 researchers regarding the role of the FAIR principles in their reuse of data. *What challenges do researchers face regarding the FAIR aspects of data reuse, and in which ways could these aspects improve?* The interviews provided important insight into some of the challenges they face and possible tools that could facilitate the process of reusing data. The results are covered in [Chapter 3](#). Third, we conducted a quantitative survey in the same five European countries included in the NIS. The quantitative survey included questions regarding data reuse and knowledge of EOSC and FAIR principles. *How often do researchers (re)use different types of data and which aspects play a role in reuse?* These topics are covered in [Chapter 4](#).

1 National Initiatives Survey: Events, Discussions, and Feedback

1.1 The role of policies

1.1.1 Introduction

Policies are cornerstones of open science and findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) data. Whether there are national and institutional policies in place and what they address is essential to establishing open science practices in the research community. The webinar organized by EOSC-Pillar on October 27th, 2020, aimed at outlining existing research on open science policies as well as getting insights from experts working in the field. This section contains the summary of the webinar. In the first part, the findings on policies of the NIS conducted by EOSC-Pillar were presented. Sections 1.1.2 and 1.1.3 include an overview of the presentations. In the second part of the webinar, expert panelists discussed policies from different angles and enriched the discussion with their experiences in different fields (e.g. universities, funding organizations, open science initiatives). Section 1.1.4 contains the key arguments of the discussion. More information on the webinar, the agenda and the recording are available on the [EOSC-Pillar website](#).

1.1.2 Presentation 1: Policy status quo: open science and FAIR data

EOSC-Pillar, as one of the regional EOSC support projects, aims at coordinating national and regional initiatives on open data and services in five countries: Austria, Belgium, France, Germany and Italy. The project conducted a survey comprising also the current status on the existence and content of policies that aim at supporting open science and FAIR data (Bodlos et al., 2020). During her presentation (2020), Lisa Hönegger gave an overview of the survey results with a focus on universities and funding bodies.

EOSC-Pillar has asked representatives of **funding bodies** whether their organization impose(s) rules for funding on grant recipients regarding several aspects of open science and FAIR data. According to the gathered data, data management plans (40%) and open access publications (36%) are most common among binding

regulations. Funding bodies have regulations in place for open research data (32%), the compliance of data to the FAIR principles (32%), the publication of data in a repository (28%), and the long-term availability of research data (28%). However, only two of 25 funding bodies who responded indicated to condition grants on the publication of data in a certified repository. Of course, forcing grant receivers to comply with certain regulations is not the only way to foster open science practices. As the NIS shows, up to 40% of the funding bodies also encourage applicants to pursue open science and FAIR data standards.

EOSC-Pillar also surveyed representatives of **universities** as promoters of open science. The results show that more than half of the universities have policies and formal regulations in place. However, EOSC-Pillar noted large differences between the five countries: Whereas all Belgian universities reported regulations for open access publications, these phenomenon is less prevalent in the other countries. Compared to open access publications, universities less frequently launch regulations in other fields of open science and FAIR data. More than one quarter regulate the publication of data in a repository and research data management (RDM). Even less enforce the long-term availability of research data, publication of data, and the compliance of data to the FAIR principles.

Similar to the funding bodies, universities do not only rely on binding regulations, but also nudge affiliated researchers to take up open science practices: Roughly one third indicated the presence of informal regulations. Despite these formal and informal regulations, some universities still refrain from implementing them.

1.1.3 Presentation 2: Policies as an instrument in the research life cycle

As a second input presentation, Vanessa Proudman and Joy Davidson (2020) offered glimpses into their work on open science policies across Europe: One aim of [FAIRsFAIR](#) is promoting the FAIR principles and one way to do so is via policies ([Sveinsdottir et al., 2020](#)). Last year, [SPARC Europe](#), in collaboration with other organizations, analyzed policies of **funding bodies**, especially with regard to open science ([Fosci et al., 2019](#)). Similar to the results of the National Initiatives Survey, they found that open access policies are more common among funding bodies than other policies. [Fosci et al. \(2019\)](#) reported the following:

- Open access: Of the 61 funding organizations in the analysis, 60% have adopted an open access policy. The vast majority of these even have obligatory regulations. 39% of the funding bodies have renounced an open access policy. However, the authors found that 50% of the 24 funding organizations are working towards such an open access policy ([Fosci et al., 2019](#), 6).

- Open science: Of all 61 funding organizations in the analysis, 31% have an open science policy in place. Of these 19 organizations, 63% have adopted a research data policy specifically for data. These numbers also imply that 69% of the funding organizations do not have adopted such policies, but a substantial share (21%) are pursuing this goal (Fosci et al., 2019, 6).
- Besides, funding bodies audit compliance with open access policies more frequently than other policies (Fosci et al., 2019, 7).

However, Vanessa Proudman concluded that there is progress in the development of policies, hence, the landscape may very well change in the future. SPARC Europe has also conducted research for FAIRsFAIR on **national policies** (Sveinsdottir et al., 2020). Key results are: The FAIR principles are part of several national policies, but not of all (Sveinsdottir et al., 2020, 16). Likewise, a definition of research data is not part of all policies. However, the speaker highlights the national plan for open science in France as an example of a clearly defined national policy. Concerning mandates or requirements rather than recommendations to sharing data, SPARC Europe/FAIRsFAIR observed that several national policies recommend sharing data, but binding regulations are the exception rather than the rule (Sveinsdottir et al., 2020, 12). Likewise, data management plans are more frequently recommended than required (Sveinsdottir et al., 2020, 17).

Following the principle that data should be as open as possible but as closed as necessary, SPARC Europe found that only a minority of the national policies contained clear specifications on the justifications for not publishing research data. Noteworthy examples are the UK, Slovenia, and Norway (Sveinsdottir et al., 2020, 13–14). An important aspect of open science are incentives for sharing data, e.g. to enhance the prestige of publishing data and to encourage citing data. Only a minority of national policies (e.g. Switzerland, Ireland, Norway, and the UK) contain expectations regarding data citations (Sveinsdottir et al., 2020, 17–18).

Of course, adopting policies is only the first step. Therefore, SPARC Europe has also investigated whether funding organizations follow up on whether the requirements have been fulfilled. The survey among 35 funding organization shows that compliance with open access policies is regulated more frequently than compliance with other aspects of open science. Funding organizations most frequently indicated that a lack of adequate monitoring infrastructure or tools was responsible for the absence of systematic monitoring. (Fosci et al., 2019, 22–24).

FAIRsFAIR formulated several recommendations on policies (Davidson et al., 2020). One key recommendation is to formulate a common set of FAIR policy elements (Davidson et al., 2020, 8). Other recommendations refer to enhancing the accessibility, the version control of policies, and comparability via machine-readability. In terms of measurement, there is no widely acknowledged consensus on how to measure FAIRness especially with respect to discipline specific differences. Hence,

one challenge is to find a set of minimal viable metrics for FAIR data (Proudman and Davidson, 2020)¹. Also, the speaker suggests to **reward** good practice, but where necessary, **penalties** for non-compliance should be considered. (Proudman and Davidson, 2020, 23).

1.1.4 Summary of the expert discussion

This section contains an overview of the most salient arguments made in the discussion. This summary does neither implicate a consensus among all panelists nor that all participants stated their view on all topics. The panelists were Joy Davidson (Digital Curation Center), Matthias Fingerhuth (FDM NRW), Sverker Holmgren (The Guild), Jan Hrušák (EOSC Landscape Working Group), Vanessa Proudman (SPARC Europe) and Marie Timmermann (Science Europe). The moderators were Rob Carillo (EOSC-Pillar) and Federica Tanlongo (EOSC-Pillar).

Policy making

- When creating open science policies, it is important to keep in mind their practicability for those who have to implement them.
- Top-down pressure may be counterproductive: Policies have the potential to move open science forward, especially if they are designed in a bottom-up and top-down process at the same time. Especially important is the support of and the acceptance by researchers.
- Researchers have to be provided with the means and infrastructure to comply with policies.
- Communicating the existence and content of policies is very important. Likewise, communication concerning the effects of compliance with policies, e.g. highlighting best practice examples, is vital.
- Countries differ regarding the funding structure of research and career opportunities for researchers. Consequently, different types of organizations (e.g. universities or funding bodies) bear a different weight when it comes to the impact of their policies on open science.
- Open science can be considered as a paradigm change of how science and research should be conducted. Therefore, the implementation of this change requires time and patience. We are still at the beginning of this process and therefore should not expect researchers to change the way they work from one day to another due to a policy.

¹See also the consultation on the [FAIRsFAIR](#) website, last accessed 13 February 2021.

- Encouraging open access publications and policies thereon has been a goal since the 1990s. This change was more simply achieved since it only required a change in the business model of publishers. On the contrary, opening data requires an entirely new concept in academia.

Communication

- Effective communication is a key factor for successful change. Since there are many stakeholders involved in opening science, they need to work together closely to use synergies and knowledge. In addition, the benefits of open science need to be communicated clearly.
- Communication is especially important to connect actors who stir, design and implement policies. Different stakeholder groups (e.g politicians and university managers) have similar discussions, but do not collaborate enough.
- Similar to how researchers need time to adapt to the concept of open science, drafting policies on this matter should not be rushed. Instead, improved communication between policy makers allows for exchanging experiences and for aligning policies.

Alignment

- The harmonization of policies throughout institutions and countries is key to empowering EOSC, connecting researchers and data across borders.
- Policies have the potential to move open science forward, especially if they are well aligned across countries and organizations.
- Researchers value alignment as they e.g. receive funding from different funding agencies. Consequently, aligned policies and regulations are an advantage for researchers.
- Too much pushing for alignment may be counterproductive: there are some country-specific particularities that need to be considered. Conventions also differ across disciplines and need to be respected.
- Open science policies exist at several levels: the institutional, regional, national, and European levels. These layers have to be respected when drafting policies as top-down pressure may not be successful in the long run if researchers are not engaged.
- An important aspect of alignment is streamlining expectations of FAIR data: We need to find a definition for the basic criteria of FAIR data that is commonly agreed upon. Hence, minimum criteria as well as optional guidelines for assessing when data are required.

Rewards and penalties

Concerning measures to enhance the compliance with research data management policies, the discussion showed a preference for support and rewards over penalties.

- The primary goal of many organizations is to support researchers, not to penalize non-compliance. If researchers do not comply with policies, the first step should be to support them better and discuss their needs.
- Infrastructures, resources and knowledge how to comply with policies are essential and must be provided. Otherwise, researchers cannot comply – no matter how grave the penalties may be.
- Rewards are also a key factor to enhance compliance. If there are rewards for opening research, researchers will more likely comply.
- Communication and framing are important: Referring to policies as guidelines is more attractive to researchers than calling them regulations. Framing policies as a “guideline to get your reward” is probably the best way to motivate researchers to comply with policies.
- However, if there are no consequences for researchers who repeatedly violate regulations and do not even try to comply, this may undermine the policies.

1.1.5 Conclusion and recommendations

Conclusion and recommendations

In the discussion, the experts drew the following conclusions on what is needed to enhance the effectiveness of and compliance with policies. First, good communication is needed to make the content, the use and the benefits of open science policies clear. Also, communication between the different stakeholders is important, to exchange experiences, ensure an adequate level of alignment of policies and to learn from best practice examples. A second key factor is to put effort in motivating and supporting researchers to implement open science policies, e.g. by providing the necessary resources, clear guidelines, and rewards. Last but not least, making science and data open and FAIR is a paradigm change in academia that will take time.

1.2 Health and biodiversity

1.2.1 Summary

The French-speaking webinar was held on September 16th, 2021, with the help of the EOSC-Pillar partner Trust-IT. It was organized by Gilles Mathieu from the National Institute of Health and Medical Research (INSERM), Yosra Sanaa (INSERM), and Geneviève Romier from the National Center of Scientific Research (CNRS). The (open) event was dedicated to health and biodiversity but the advertisements were disseminated via non-thematic ways. The agenda was organized in three parts: the first one was a presentation dedicated to “EOSC for researchers”. In the second part, the results of the EOSC-Pillar NIS were presented.

1.2.2 Participants

Registration was mandatory. In addition to the 4 EOSC-Pillar members and 6 panel members, 37 people registered (8 researchers, 29 people in charge of research support). The maximum of simultaneous attendees was 29. The numbers are too low to get a valuable trend, but the figure underscores the diversity of the affiliations and localizations. The scientific domains of participants included: agriculture, feeding and environment, astronomy, biodiversity, biodiversity, forest ecology, bioinformatics, bioinformatics, biology, health, informatics, data science, chemistry, biology, computing for biodiversity, biogeography, digital humanities, environment, epidemiology, food safety, genetics, high energy physics, grid computing, worldwide LHC computing grid (WLCG), high performance computing, big data, informatics, forest environment, information sciences, internal medicine, infectious disease, life sciences, math-informatics, medical research, metabolomics, databases, neurosciences, open science, particle physics, physical biochemistry, chemistry, public health, research data, sciences, and scientific and technical information.

1.2.3 Questions about EOSC for researchers

The questions asked following the talks denote that EOSC needs to be more disseminated: *Where is the EOSC datacenter? Does EOSC deliver a digital object identifier (DOI) to the data deposited?* Thus, presentations covering services such as the EOSC Marketplace are crucial. The panelists were chosen to represent different affiliations, disciplines, and activities in order to reflect the research landscape. The panel was moderated by Gilles Mathieu. There were six panelists: Abdelkader Amzert (INSERM), Volker Beckmann, French Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation (MESRI), Alexandre Dehne Garcia, French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (Inrae), François Druelle, French National Museum of Natural History (MNHN), Camille Lobry (INSERM), Marie-Claude Quidoz (Center of Functional and Evolutionary Ecology (CEFE)/CNRS). This summary neither implies consensus among all panelists, nor that all partici-

pants stated their view on all topics. The panel members' activities and responsibilities are diverse. Depending on their activities, they have different knowledge levels of EOSC. Two of them are researchers. One works in the fields of archaeology and palaeoanthropology on locomotion evolution. The other one is in charge of a research team in a hospital. The team works with genomics data and multiomics (including patients' health data). Two others are involved in the IT scientific management of their organization. One person is special adviser for the implementation of the European Open Science Cloud in France at the Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation and involved (elected) in the EOSC steering board. One panelist is in charge of the observation data platform in a large laboratory in ecology with many research topics that aims to understand life at large. Questions were divided into 4 slots.

1.2.4 Introduction

- Training and support: how EOSC can help structure the support and training aspects of services.
- Introduction of participants: summary of positions regarding Research Infrastructures and European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) in their discipline, links with other communities, disciplines and structures in others countries (especially for data sharing).
- FAIR Data: FAIR principles, needs, requirements, and tools needed to share data at the European level.
- Data management: familiarity with data licenses, problems in their use, solutions.

1.2.5 FAIR data and data management

- FAIR was well known as a concept, but it needs to be implemented and consistent with other research initiatives.
- Data may be stored locally and not FAIR before publication, but raw data should be deposited on disciplinary international repositories when the articles are published (mandatory by the editors/publishers).
- In some cases there are no guidelines regarding metadata, and data is often unusable. Researchers do not have the means to share data in their work because they both lack guidelines and appropriate tools to reference them.
- Researchers currently don't have accurate knowledge of the data licenses and mostly use the same ones. Thanks to preprint archives, they are beginning to learn that.

- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance and sensitive data protection is not easy.
- CEFE set up a thematic axis on data life cycles. At the time of the workshop, three people were in charge of this topic (with different types of expertise). They focused on quality, and identified that when data are manually collected (e.g. biodiversity data), they lack resources to validate them properly in order to share them subsequently. When data are simultaneously related to different topics, it is not easy to find the right metadata to allow multidisciplinary work. They share data via a disciplinary repository. They think they are not sufficiently aware of the licenses to use them correctly.
- At INSERM, they are looking for solutions to work with heterogeneous and interdisciplinary data. They encountered issues with data quality and business models for the cohorts (long time life data). In certain circumstances, such as the Covid crisis, research has to align with the medical sciences and health monitoring. There is also a need to share data with other social activities. Repositories need to be built for the long term (variants survey standardization, vaccination, etc.). The experience of the COVID database shows that a really efficient incentive may be competitive reasons.
- At INRAE, data description, formats, quality and of course they need repositories need to be improved. They need common semantics to be able to cross data. They also need to provide data analysis services in addition to data that they share. It's not easy to move data and they need to allow the analysis close to the data (see the EOSC-Pillar dedicated case to that point). They need human support to help researchers to share FAIR data and INRAE set up a human organization for this support. Licenses are difficult, and there are differences between organizations' points of view. The data need to be tracked.

1.2.6 Training and support

- In the discussion, it was established that all types of training at all levels are needed. Training and support are crucial. Face to face is preferable, if possible. Online documentation is improving in the fields of archaeology and palaeoanthropology. Webinars are useful.
- Practical training with real data is lacking.
- English is mandatory, however the support staff often does not have the same level of English as researchers. They need documentation and training in French. Documentation at the European level is in English, yet the documentation close to the user should be in French. This implies technical training in local language and English for scientific topics.

- There is a need to curate the documentation or to select the most pertinent support.
- The human support effort needs to be shared.
- FAIR data are at the core of EOSC. Training, guidelines and help to FAIRization are accessible through the EOSC Portal. MESRI supports this work and is going to provide “[RDG-RechercheDataGouv](#)” that is coordinated by Inrae.
- Information on the new European calls, information on EOSC at large, and training dedicated to decision-makers are necessary.
- EOSC Ambassador program disseminates EOSC information.

1.2.7 Conclusion and recommendations

Conclusion and recommendations

All types of training and at all levels are needed: information, curated documentation, training, support about FAIRization, metadata, data sharing, data tracking, GDPR-specific points, sensitive data protection, and licenses. The French Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation supports the communities, coordinates the initiatives, and manages discussions to facilitate the integration of French infrastructures in EOSC. MESRI supports the work around EOSC and is going to provide “[RDG-RechercheDataGouv](#)”, coordinated by INRAE.

1.3 Motivations and obstacles: the EOSC catalogue

1.3.1 Summary

The French speaking workshop was held on March 2nd-March 3rd, 2022. It was organized by Marine Vernet (IFREMER), Gilles Mathieu (INSERM), and Geneviève Romier (CNRS). The (closed) event was dedicated to the motivations and obstacles to the registration of services in the EOSC catalogue. The agenda was separated into three parts: in the first part, the context (EOSC-Pillar and its National Initiatives survey) was presented. The second one was a short presentation of each participant. The third part was a panel discussion. This section presents both the presentations and the main points raised during the panel discussion.

1.3.2 Event invitations

The organizers invited a panel of participants. The objective was to have diversity in the roles, type of work and implication in EOSC (via projects or activities). Some of them were involved in computing and data analysis regional or thematic centres. Others were involved in a scientific community and in the coordination of a group of users. They were affiliated either to IFREMER, INSERM and CNRS or to universities.

1.3.3 Event preparation

In order to prepare the workshop, questions were sent to the panelists some days before the meeting. The questions were: *Do you work with a catalogue of services? Do you think that those catalogues are useful? EOSC is setting up a services catalogue—do you think to have the opportunity to use it? If yes in what context?* The questions for the **service providers** included: *Do you wish to publish some of the services you offer in the [EOSC catalogue](#) in the short, middle or long term? What type of services? For what reasons? Do you foresee obstacles for this registration (technical, operational, strategic, financial, laws)?* The questions to the **service users** included: *What services would you like to find in the EOSC catalogue? For what reasons? What criteria are important to publish in the catalogue to allow you to choose or select the service you need? Would some of these criteria constitute potential obstacles to their usage?*

1.3.4 Panelists

Cyrille Toulet (Université de Lille) works at the regional mesocenter² of Lille University. This regional computing centre is part of federations such as [France Grilles](#), [European Grid Infrastructure \(EGI\)](#) and [the French Institut of Bioinformatics \(IFB\)](#). Violaine Louvet (CNRS) is manager of Gricad that proposes data and computing infrastructures to scientific communities. She is involved in EOSC-Pillar (7.4 - PICO2 that works on interoperability between computing infrastructures). Didier Reibex (Université de Bourgogne) is manager of the regional mesocenter of the University of Bourgogne (currently merging with the mesocenter of Franche Comté). This centre is part of the network of mesocenters called the MesoNet project. Rodolphe Thiebaut (INSERM) is professor at the University of Bordeaux, Director of the department of research in public health (600 people), and he conducts research activities in the field of epidemiology with health data. He is involved in the strategy of the IT unit in relationship with France Grilles, the regional mesocenter, etc. Gilbert Maudire (IFREMER) is in charge of the IT department at IFREMER. He is also responsible for the ocean part of [Data Terra](#) and involved in the EOSC-Pillar Use Case 6.2. Mickaël Dequidt (IFREMER) works at the infrastructure team and is member of the administrators' group for storage and high-performance computing (HPC) at DATARMOR (storage, analysis and computing infrastructure for marine data).

1.3.5 Discussion

The centers generally publish a catalogue of their services. The content focuses on the users' point of view to help them to know what the centres propose. Their users are mainly local. Foreign users or users from other regions are accepted when they have common projects with a local user. They also work with research infrastructures such as [Huma-Num](#) or Data Terra.

The EOSC catalogue could be useful to find specific services they cannot offer. They think their users will not search directly in the EOSC catalogue because they don't know what is EOSC. They think that the percentage of researchers who know what is EOSC is close to 0%. The users need support to know what they could search and what are the most pertinent services for their needs. A large catalogue should be linked to such a support in order to be of interest for the researchers. They also think that because the mesocenters were set up and continuously adapted to the needs of their users. Looking for other services may be an exception.

The mesocenters are able to open their services to other universities. They may describe their services in the EOSC catalogue in order to gain more visibility and to allow the users coming from other regions to benefit from their services. A better

²A mesocenter is a data and computing center that is generally part of one or several universities and whose users are local researchers. They generally have several types of computers: cloud, middle size high performance computing (HPC) computers, visualization services for the data. They support local and regional users and they may accept them on the basis of a scientific topic.

knowledge of the EOSC catalogue and the services that are described would allow a better support to help them. The panel mentioned that the mesocenters may be the first step to help and support researchers. For all users, a support is necessary even if they are skilled enough in IT to use European resources.

There is also a need of data catalogues because data is the research core. At IFREMER, they propose data catalogues (with associated services). IFREMER uses the EOSC Marketplace for Seadatanet (vocabulary, data discovery services) and marine services of Copernicus will be described in EOSC. IFREMER is registered as services provider. They don't use the catalogue to look for services because it is a generic catalogue and the users know the existing services in their domain.

The main obstacle to opening their resources to other users is the limitation of their human resources to support them. In addition, their resources are already used at almost 100% of their capacity. The openness should be limited to be able to support the additional users. The support is the main added-value of the mesocenters. Too many users is a risk to the quality of this support. There is a doubt on the usability of a potential financial compensation for additional users. Could this income be used to hire human resources?

Opening the services offers visibility and could give opportunity to new collaborations. Sharing is an academic principle but human resources limitations is an issue. Thematic services are generally set up in the framework of projects and built on e-infrastructures services that are available only during the project's duration. Then these thematic services are not sustainable and cannot be registered. Some services (of IFREMER) are sustainable but the access is limited to known and identified users. In this case the service registration in the catalogue is not of interest.

Mesocenters and thematic computing and storage infrastructures are used to give access to their services to European partners in the context of joint projects and have adapted their service level agreements (SLAs) accordingly. However, if these services were to be offered at European level, opening them up to a large number of transnational users could be more complex (mostly in terms of security).

At IFREMER the communities are used to share the main part of their data. They also need to share them to comply with the open data requirements. The main obstacles are the security constraints to protect the HPC computer and data of restricted usage. In addition, they encounter technical issues regarding open data. Large volumes of data are not easy to move and need to be analyzed in a near location. Another point is the need to improve the interoperability with other disciplines that are interested in using their data.

1.3.6 Conclusions and recommendations

Conclusion and recommendations

- The mesocenters are tailored to the needs of their dedicated users and there is a low probability that they will need to look for other services elsewhere. In this case, the support offered by the mesocenters is key.
- Currently, the mesocenters are lacking concrete knowledge of EOSC. A recommendation would be to provide the mesocenters staff with a better knowledge of EOSC.
- The main interest of the EOSC catalogue is the visibility it offers that may give opportunity for new collaborations between mesocenters.
- Data catalogues are also necessary.
- A lot of services are set up in the framework of projects and built on e-infrastructures services that are available only for a limited amount of time. Then, these thematic services are not sustainable and cannot be registered. A way to sustain the most useful services built in the framework of projects would be useful to avoid loss of resources and efficiency.
- The main obstacle to open resources to other users is the limitation of available human resources to support them. In addition, resources are already used at almost 100% of their capacity. Mesocenters are very careful to ensure a high quality of user support because support is their main added-value. Too many users is a risk to the quality of this support. Then they think that openness of their services should be limited to be able to support the additional users with the right level of quality.
- There is doubt regarding the usability of a potential financial compensation for additional users. Could this income be used to hire human resources?
- Currently, there is no way to analyze the large volumes of data close to their location. Possible security issues to be taken into account when considering opening services to a large number of transnational users.
- Interoperability between disciplines must be improved (e.g. vocabulary, standards).

1.4 Mini-hackathon

1.4.1 Summary

The mini-hackathon took place in the face-to-face call on April 21st, 2022. The main goal of the hackathon was to present the NIS datasets and to learn how to access and analyze the data. The agenda included an introduction, an introduction to RStudio, and descriptive data analysis in the D4Science environment created by WP7. There were 17 participants.

1.4.2 Introduction

Yann Le Franc introduced the agenda and discussed the purpose of the mini-hackathon. In a first step, the goal was to familiarize oneself with the data. In a second step, questions were collected using D4Science for the second session. The idea was that the participants then analyze the data and/or the questionnaire themselves. This way, questions could be collected for the second session on May 19th, 2022.

1.4.3 Session 1: April 21st, 2022

1.4.4 Work Package 3 Datasets

Following the introduction, Theresa Kernecker, the task leader of WP3 presented the National Initiatives Survey. Specifically, she showed how the data can be downloaded from the [Austrian Social Science Data Archive \(AUSSDA\)](#). The slides included all of the relevant links to download the data and obtain information regarding the individual datasets and the questionnaire. Next the prepared R script was presented in the D4Science environment using RStudio ([RStudio Team, 2020](#)). The scripts included the codes for descriptive univariate and bivariate analyses that would be useful for any type of future presentation or report. Since the NI Surveys contain mostly nominal data, the appropriate analyses include frequency tables, crosstabs, bar graphs, and pie charts. The script included the corresponding R codes and options including both the basic plot commands and commands from the ggplot2 package ([Wickham, 2016](#)) for data visualization. The examples drew heavily on the short version of the dataset. Specifically, they used the questions on how familiar organizations are with FAIR principles and the perceived benefit of EOOSC. The slides included all of the codes in the R script as well as an exercise. Participants learned how to import each version of the dataset and create a graph with a given variable. Given time constraints, these exercises were saved until the following session. These codes and all materials are available in the EOOSC-Pillar Repository and in the D4Science environment. The scripts can be used to analyze any other variable in the dataset and serve as a starting point for further analysis. Following the presentation, one participant asked whether it was possible to analyze two variables from different datasets, in order to compare different variables from

the NIS Dataset and the Researcher Survey. This was one of the questions that was addressed with the corresponding code on May 19th, 2022. After the presentations, the participants were granted access to D4Science and we discussed how we would prepare using D4Science communication and analysis functionalities for the next session in May.

1.4.5 Work Package 7 D4science

Next, Leonardo Candela presented the virtual research environment [D4Science](#). The Virtual Research Environment is conceived to provide EOSC-Pillar members with a virtual laboratory to experiment by using an array of analytics tools. The environment supports the development and integration environment for R, Python, and other software languages. The environments are not for large-scale processing. They are conceived to support the integration, testing, and validation of your script in the D4Science distributed computing facility. Thereafter, Leonardo explained how the environment works.

First, Leonardo presented the analytics Engine (DataMiner). The DataMiner permits the execution of an array of analytics methods by transparently relying on distributed computing infrastructure. Executions can run either on multi-core machines or on different computational platforms, such as D4Science. Second, Leonardo presented the RStudio environment in D4Science. The RStudio provides an integrated development environment for R. It includes a console, a syntax-highlighting editor, and it enables code execution. Tools for plotting are also included. This RStudio environment is 1) preconfigured with libraries and packages to ease the execution of common data analytics tasks, and 2) provides seamless access to the Workspace enabling sharing of resources with other members much easier. Third, Leonardo explained how the [JupyterHub](#) works. JupyterHub enables the exploitation of computational environments and resources without burdening users with installation and maintenance tasks. The JupyterHub environment is 1) preconfigured with libraries and packages to ease the execution of common data analytics tasks, and 2) provides access to the Workspace enabling sharing of resources with other members much easier.

1.4.6 Session 2: May 19th, 2022

The hackathon's second session focused on answering the questions that were posted in D4Science since the previous session. The questions were posted in the D4Science environment: *How can we compare the demand of researchers regarding data reuse and the actual supply of organizations to make them available? Is there a relationship for e-infrastructures between the type of services they propose and whether they acquire revenues other than funding? Is there a link between discipline-specific infrastructures and whether they have regulations or policies on open access publications? Are there differences in funding depending on the disciplines they work for?*

To answer the questions based on the datasets presented in the previous session, the participants were divided into two groups. Both groups worked on the questions in R or in Python and calculated correlations between the variables pertaining to the questions. Both groups found different ways to visualize the data, via heatmaps or basic univariate analysis. The sessions will continue since several participants concurred regarding the usefulness of analyzing data in the D4Science environment.

1.4.7 Conclusion and recommendations

Conclusion and recommendations

The hackathon was a useful way to familiarize project members with the Work Package 3 datasets containing information about infrastructures and researchers. It was not only an advantageous way to get to know the data, but it was also helpful to participants without experience with RStudio or Python. At the end of the second session, it was determined that these sessions should be continued. Thus, looking towards the future of EOSC, hackathons are a practical and straight-forward way to familiarize users with data sources, data analysis, and different types of data available all at once. This type of event should be organized more regularly in the future.

1.5 EOSC webinar event in Germany

1.5.1 Introduction

Overall, 140 people participated in the “Germany and EOSC for researchers” webinar on February 23rd, 2022. An expert panel discussed the relationship between EOSC and NFDI³. A brief introduction on the role and position of NFDI by Sophie Kraft of the NFDI directorate was followed by presentations representing two communities of the German research landscape. Christoph Eberl of the University of Freiburg pointed at the data integration and sharing efforts of the materials science community and the need for a cultural change. Kay Graf of the Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg explained how services of the [ESCAPE cluster](#) that are built on the EOSC core services (implemented by EOSC-Future) help to make scientific results accessible and enable interdisciplinary research.

1.5.2 Live services and data in the EOSC Portal

In the second part of the event, best practice examples of live services came on stage. Before, Rebecca Reichenbach of the Fraunhofer IWM demonstrated how and which data services can be found in the EOSC portal⁴. Marco Kulüke of the German Climate Computing Center showed how climatology research uses services provided by different EOSC partners and links these in a unified workflow. Representing the Biology community, Anton Güntsch of the Free University of Berlin, introduced the Global Genome Biodiversity Network, a world wide used service pre-dating EOSC. It showed that standards, to ensure interoperability, are paramount when publishing scientific results. The resources needed to compute and analyze data are offered by the “Container and GPU as a Service” (CGAAS) of the Institut Pluridisciplinaire Hubert Curien in Strasbourg. In his presentation Jerome Pansanel of the same institute showed the steps taken to integrate the service in the EOSC ecosystem.

1.5.3 Panel discussion

The event ended with a panel discussion which panelist Marie Czuray of University of Vienna kicked off with a pitch on the EOSC-Pillar Ambassadors Program that offers support in promoting EOSC. Subsequently she and the panelists Raphael Ritz of the Max Planck Computing and Data Facility, Birgit Gemeinholzer of the University of Kassel and Achim Streit of the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology shed their views on engagement of German researchers with EOSC and the interaction with and the role of NFDI and EOSC. The panel acknowledged the importance of both initiatives and suggested finding apt communication methods to upkeep the information exchange and to learn from each other in order to prevent disparate developments. Further

³NFDI is the German mandated member of the EOSC Association.

⁴<https://eosc-portal.eu/>

it was considered important that only trusted data repositories and services will be offered and it is necessary to have examples of attractive data services from both NFDI and EOSC, even if these are slightly competitive. The video recordings and copies of the presentations can be found on the [workshop webpage](#).

1.5.4 Questions

The question and answer session and was moderated by Jos van Wezel (KIT). The following questions were asked, followed by the corresponding answers. *How can our research data become interoperable with EOSC?* As a response, the EOSC marketplace and portal were recommended. *What is the best metadata standard to describe software? Or what are equally suited options?* [The Data Alliance](#), [de-RSE](#), and [CodeMeta](#) were recommended. The next question was: *You talked about “providing VO services”, what do you mean by that, i.e. the data services (SCS, TAP, etc), or the software to publish VO services (Software as a Service (SaaS))?* Another question was: *In your presentation, you said “we discuss about onboarding the software behind the services.” Where do you discuss that?* The response pointed to [ESCAPE WP4](#). Next, a question was asked about SCCS systems: *There are currently only Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety (SCCS) systems (e.g gitlab) but no agreed way to assign identifiers. One can always use Zenodo to get a DOI, but no general Metadata schema is worked out (afaik)*”. The answer referred to the ESCAPE approach: “The ESCAPE approach is that stable versions are published to Zenodo (with a crosswalk from CodeMeta meta data to Zenodo MetaData). However, [Software Heritage](#) is also archiving all commits and provides a reliable identifier to every line of code.” Another response pointed to a working group in this area: “For software, you have take a look at the outcome of the [following working group](#).” The next question asked about where to find ecological data in EOSC: *Against the background [of the] green deal, I wonder where to find biodiversity/ecological data in EOSC? Subsumed in existing categories? Is there a need for a community to approach EOSC to have such a biodiversity?* The response was: “Certainly the development of such a green deal category would be of interest but people need to confine to whatever they can.” The next question was: *Again, back to data as a “private good” in general. Actual “live” research data are available on any cloud platform/portal...what to do if this data collides with publishers’ interests when meant to be published? e.g: put embargo on data in the cloud until paper is published?* The last question was: *What does EOSC offer that NFDI doesn’t already offer national researchers - what is the added value in your opinion?* The response was: “[.] I guess I think that message should be passed on in communication: an extra European layer for interoperability and frameworks that can filter down to national level.”

1.6 FAIR data: management, gaps, and solutions

1.6.1 Introduction

The aim of the webinar titled “FAIR Data: Management Gaps and Solutions” jointly organized by EOSC-Pillar project and Data Infrastructure Capacity for EOSC (DICE) project on January 31st, 2022, was to present potential solutions to solve the FAIR data management challenges identified by the landscaping study carried out by WP3 team of the EOSC Pillar project. Even though most of the main actors involved in management of data are familiar with the concept of FAIRness, FAIR principles are applied to the data holdings only in part due to the challenges, often also technical, that FAIR Data Management presents. A response can be the use and integration of data management services designed with the aim of increasing the overall FAIRness of data.

The webinar was opened by DICE Project Coordinator Debora Testi from the Interuniversity Consortium for Automatic Computing of Northeastern Italy ([CINECA](#)). Next, EOSC-Pillar’s Federica Tanlongo from the Gestione Ampliamento Rete Ricerca ([GARR](#)) presented “FAIRness of data in EU countries - a landscape study” which highlighted several gaps on keeping research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. Following the presentation of the FAIR data management gaps in the EOSC-Pillar countries, DICE representatives Claudia Martens ([German Climate Center \(DKRZ\)](#)), Themis Zamani ([GRNET](#)), and Chris Ariyo ([CSC](#)) respectively presented how [B2FIND](#) can aggregate data repositories and help increase findability, how [B2HANDLE](#) can provide persistent identifiers for research data, and how research data can be made available and reusable with [B2SHARE](#). At the end, an open discussion took place with the help of the Slido platform to give input to the discussion and increase the engagement of the participants.

The event was open to everybody prior registration and was disseminated both on EOSC Pillar project and DICE project websites⁵. The target audience were researchers, repository managers, research community managers or actors in the EOSC community that are interested in the practicalities of handling and producing research data, all interested in making their research activities more FAIR. One hundred ninety six people from different European countries were registered for the event and the maximum number of simultaneous attendees was 146. 84% of the registered people registered from the EOSC-Pillar project website while 16% registered from the DICE project website. The distribution of their roles was heterogeneous with a predominance of people from University and Research infrastructure.

⁵The agenda, the recordings and the slides used during the presentations are available on the [DICE Project website](#).

1.6.2 EOSC Pillar contribution: FAIRness of data in EU countries

EOSC-Pillar is one of the four EOSC regional projects covering the implementation of EOSC in Austria, Belgium, France, Germany and Italy. As part of its mandate, in 2021 it conducted a comprehensive survey which gathered input from at least 600 research infrastructures, e-infrastructures, universities and funding bodies. It provided a snapshot of the state of national initiatives on open data and services in the five EOSC-Pillar countries. A key topic of the survey was data management and FAIRness. An entire section of the survey was dedicated to assessing the needs and difficulties researchers face when re-using data, in particular what hinders and what facilitates the findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability of data from a researcher's perspective. During her presentation, Federica Tanlongo gave an overview of the survey results regarding the above-mentioned section. Research infrastructures, e-infrastructures, universities and funding bodies stated to feel between "familiar" or "very familiar" with FAIR data principles.

Some relevant insights came out of the survey to the representatives of e-infrastructures category who manage repositories and data related digital infrastructures. When it came to rating how FAIR their own data holdings were, most of the respondents were only "somewhat FAIR". When asked whether their e-infrastructure provides a search feature for metadata, only about half of respondents said that they have this feature fully implemented. As for whether they provide their data catalogue in a machine-readable format, only slightly more than 40% indicated that they have it fully implemented. The presenter, Federica Tanlongo observed, "The link between FAIR, open science and EOSC in general is not always so immediate as one would imagine." Insights on country trends supporting this assertion were highlighted:

- In Austria, while universities, research infrastructures and e-infrastructures generally show high familiarity with FAIR principles, their familiarity with EOSC is rather low with only less than 16% being part of an organization that facilitates integration into EOSC.
- In Germany, there appears to be less familiarity with the FAIR principles with only 50% of universities being familiar with them and less than 35% with regulations in place for research data management and open data as well as for other aspects of FAIR i.e. long term availability and related repositories. On the other hand, awareness of EOSC is higher with over 50% of universities indicating that EOSC will affect them and 75% expecting to benefit from it.
- In Belgium, e-infrastructures, research infrastructures and universities are familiar with FAIR, but e-infrastructures have a noted lower awareness of EOSC, with particular differences based on scientific domain/community.

- In France, e-Infrastructures, research infrastructures and universities indicated high familiarity with FAIR principles, but that user training needs to be offered in French more than English. It was observed that a centralized policy direction contributes to the higher awareness of FAIR and EOSC in general.
- In Italy, meanwhile the lack of centralized policy direction results in lower awareness of FAIR and readiness for it. Repositories concern on benefit and competitive disadvantage when sharing data (more than 35% indicated this).

Looking closer at FAIR across countries, repositories reach an average findability score of 65%. Regarding Persistent identifiers (PIDs), on average, 44% have fully implemented PIDs with 17% currently in the process of implementing them. Of the repositories that use PIDs, DOIs were the most common, followed by Handle and Uniform Resource Name (URN). As for accessibility, the majority of e-infrastructures do have accessibility policies. As for interoperability, repositories reach an average interoperability score of 65%. Across the countries, repositories have reached an average reusability score of 57%. Federica concluded that though the “FAIRness” of data seems far away, respondents do seem to be aware of it. Work towards improving it is a continuous effort requiring time and coordination with strong strategy and support from the policy level.

1.6.3 DICE contribution

Using persistent identifiers for research data with B2HANDLE, making data available and re-usable with B2SHARE, and increasing findability with B2FIND

DICE project is one of the projects funded under the Horizon 2020 Program’s [INFRAEOSC-07](#) section to build up the infrastructure of EOSC. One of its aims is to provide to all EOSC researchers and communities data management services for making their data FAIR. The services are designed to be used across all domains and thus are potentially useful to all research communities in Europe. Services presented during this webinar were suggested as a possible technical solution to fill some of the gaps identified in the survey conducted by EOSC Pillar project. All the services presented during the webinar are part of the [EUDAT B2 services suite](#). They are some of the services DICE project is providing for free until the end of the project (June 2023) and they can be requested directly via the EOSC Portal.

Themis Zamani presented B2Handle service starting her presentation highlighting the importance of persistent identifiers (PIDs), long term references to a document, a file, web page or any other digital object that allow any object to be identified persistently and uniquely by associating its reference data. B2Handle is a service to store, manage and access persistent identifiers, accessing metadata and using PID

namespaces. This service is designed to contribute to data persistency by maintaining globally unique persistent identifiers.

Chris Ariyo introduced B2Share service. B2Share is a data sharing platform where datasets can be safely stored and published. This service preserves data for a long time, shares it and puts all the necessary persistent PIDs and Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs). It addresses small to medium teams who want to make their data available to a wider community and reusable in the future.

Claudia Martens presented B2Find service, an interdisciplinary search portal for research data. The service enables findability of data stored in EUDAT data centers, in other research infrastructure or provided by different data providers. It is not only a metadata catalogue but also a metadata aggregator because all the records that are within B2Find are automatically harvested and exposed to OpenAIRE. To be published on B2Find all data are harvested from communities, the ingested metadata are mapped, and, after a validation process, they are exposed on the search portal. Different metadata standards are supported but effort is additionally put in mapping community specific metadata. The latter enables harvesting from communities that do not expose metadata in the already standardized way.

1.6.4 Summary of the open discussion

The open discussion engaged after the presentations started using some guiding questions. Here is an overview of the collected answers. The questions were as follows: [Figure 1.1](#) displays the answer to the following question: *In one/two words, what is the main obstacle to increase the FAIRness of data repositories that you commonly see?* [Figure 1.2](#) shows the answers to the following question: *What approach do you think is more appropriate to increase standardization of metadata?* [Figure 1.3](#) displays the answers to the following question: *Can training be useful to fill the gaps?* [Figure 1.4](#) shows the answers to the following question: *In one/two words, what is the main difficulty you encounter in searching for data?* [Figure 1.5](#) covers the answers to the following question: *In one/two words, what is the most important feature when making use of a data repository?* The following figures display the responses. The word clouds can be interpreted as follows: the larger the word, the more often it was mentioned.

Figure 1.1 – Main obstacles to FAIRness (N=26)

Figure 1.2 – Standardizing metadata (N=29)

Figure 1.3 – Usefulness of training (N=24)

Figure 1.4 – Main difficulties when searching for data (N=18)

Figure 1.5 – Most important features of data repositories (N=23)

1.6.5 Main Points

- It is important to make clear that themes like sustainability in terms of data preservation are crucial. Organizing this across all the different policies from national, thematic members, international institutions and getting this altogether is the most challenging part.

- One of the challenges in FAIR data management is around metadata and metadata standards. The most rated option is to make different standards interoperable. However, in practice it is not so easy to get everything interoperable when you have such different metadata coming from very different scientific domains.
- It is not so easy to make different standards interoperable in practice. There is a huge gap between the theoretical level of how this goal can be achieved and what can actually work in reality. Discussion is important but an approach based on clear use cases can help.
- It is important to keep in mind that standards evolve. Thus, interoperability is an ongoing process.
- A realistic approach to interoperability is something that stands between the option of adhere to a single standard and the approach of making different standards interoperable. It seems more feasible to start making research data interoperable at the same time but start with disciplines that have more commonalities and bring them together. B2Find is an example of good practice. It started with common terms and then added community standards.
- It is not feasible to make interoperable metadata coming from different scientific domains at a useful level without the researcher investing effort and processes to obtain community approval. On a specific level it is impossible to have “useful” links for interoperability.
- Communities have developed data and models’ interoperability strategies that might be of general interest⁶.
- Training is considered useful to fill the gaps in FAIR Data Management. It can be offered by different providers regarding various products. EOSC plays a crucial role in training or, at least, in having an overview of its core elements
- Missing metadata is considered one of the main difficulty encountered in searching for data
- Search and reliability are considered key features when making use of a data repository

⁶A proposed example of a data and models’ interoperability strategy can be found at seea.un.org.

1.6.6 Conclusion and recommendations

Conclusion and recommendations

The open discussion highlighted metadata standardization as a general issue in FAIRization of data. Hands-on experiences, getting from developing services for data management or facing real use cases, can provide useful recommendations for technical solutions to support the theoretical approaches. In general, the road to FAIR is still long but the EOSC Pillar survey's respondents, as well as the webinar attendants, seemed very aware of it. FAIRness can be represented as a continuum. It takes time, effort, and a lot of coordination and it needs strategy and support both at a technical and policy level. Often the solution is not immediate and unique but is achieved as a mix of things found that work.

2 Researchers' Data Reuse and the FAIR framework

2.1 Literature Review: Researchers' data reuse

2.1.1 Introduction

Open science implies scientific collaboration across multiple disciplines, facilitating the accessibility of research data. For the validation of research findings, research data can be stored and managed in a variety of ways including repositories and archive systems based on databases as well as cloud-based technologies [Cox and Tam \(2019\)](#). Storing and managing data should be done in a way that optimizes the reuse of data, which in turn facilitates the practice of reproducibility, transparency of scientific work and the overall success of open science ([Tenopir et al., 2011, 2015, 2020](#)).

2.1.2 Research on data reuse

Given the importance of open science, research has increasingly focused on the analysis of data sharing, use, and reuse (e.g. [Curty, 2016](#)). *Data sharing* refers to the releasing or posting of data ([Pasquetto et al., 2019; van de Sandt et al., 2019](#)), but does not automatically translate into its reuse, which is why these two concepts are not bound by a cause-and-effect relationship ([Curty, 2017](#)), although they are intertwined, e.g. [Yoon and Kim \(2019\)](#). While there is no consensus regarding the definition of reuse, it generally implies the secondary use of data for a purpose other than originally intended ([Zimmerman, 2008](#)). Reuse has also been operationalized in different ways. While some research on reuse draws on metrics such as number of downloads or publication citations ([Bishop and Kuula-Luumi, 2017](#)), others draw on analyses of researchers' perceptions, experiences, and attitudes towards the reuse of research data from both qualitative and quantitative perspectives ([Yoon, 2016; Curty, 2016; Faniel et al., 2013](#)).

Studies about data reuse differ in several ways. For example, studies based on qualitative methods tend to emphasize data reuse as a process, while quantitative methods refer to researchers' intentions to share or reuse data ([Pasquetto et al., 2019](#)). Studies have mainly approached reuse from a discipline-specific perspective,

such as earthquake engineering (Faniel and Jacobsen, 2010), social sciences (Faniel et al., 2015, 2013), ecology (Zimmerman, 2003, 2007, 2008), geophysics (Tenopir et al., 2018), earth science (Bishop et al., 2019), and biology (Yoon and Kim, 2019). Given that discipline-specific cultures are one of the main factors in driving reuse, this has complicated interdisciplinary comparisons (Pasquetto et al., 2019). Several researchers have thus approached reuse from a more transdisciplinary perspective based on survey data (Tenopir et al., 2015, 2020; Curty, 2017; Kim and Yoon, 2017) or a mixed-methods approach based on case studies, publication citations and survey data (Berghmans et al., 2017).

Research on data reuse has highlighted individuals' attitudes (e.g. trust) and experiences, disciplinary cultures and infrastructure or the research context as main explanatory factors driving reuse. Yoon (2016) highlighted the different stages of trust development associated with reuse and found that trust is dynamic and changes throughout the research process. Curty (2016) found 25 factors influencing reuse experience and perceptions grouped them into six theoretical variables: perceived benefits, perceived risks, perceived effort, social influence, facilitating conditions, and perceived reusability. She also found that perceived efficacy and efficiency of data reuse are strong predictors of reuse behavior (Curty, 2017). Curty (2017) did not find an effect of trust on reuse. In this same vein, ?showed that Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) researchers' perceived career benefit, risk and perceived effort had a significant effect on their attitudes towards data sharing. Kim and Yoon (2017) analyzed factors such as perceived usefulness, perceived concern, and availability of internal resources and data repositories influenced data reuse (Kim and Yoon, 2017). Moreover, (Faniel et al., 2015) and (Yoon and Lee, 2019) pointed to the relevance of data quality. Faniel et al. (2015) emphasized data completeness, accessibility, ease of operation, credibility, and documentation quality as key regarding satisfaction with their reuse experience (see also Yoon and Lee (2019)). Regarding how researchers find data, Berghmans et al. (2017) indicated that researchers access others' data via email or direct personal contacts, articles, supplementary material, and a wide range of websites. Berghmans et al. (2017) emphasized the role of good documentation for trusting others' data, and the institutional reputation or data cited. Overall, several studies highlighted the gap between the generally positive attitudes regarding data reuse and the actual practice of making data reusable (Tenopir et al., 2018, 2020), underscoring the necessity for more education and infrastructure in this field.

2.1.3 Research gap: Acceptance of technologies and the FAIR framework

An underused yet novel approach to data reuse based on the *acceptance of new technologies* is the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). User acceptance of new technologies and resulting opportunities are widely discussed in

the behavioral scientific literature (Dwivedi et al., 1989). Various models and approaches like the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) (Fischbein and Ajzen, 1975), the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1985), and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989) have been developed to examine individuals' drivers of acceptance and usage (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Based on a comprehensive analysis of the alternative models, Venkatesh et al. (2003) developed the UTAUT and extracted four explanatory factors that explain reuse behavior: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions (Venkatesh et al., 2003).

Beyond the focus on different explanatory factors of reuse, research has increasingly emphasized the role of specific guidelines that would facilitate data reuse. Guidelines to store research data are provided by the 'FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship' to ensure 'findability', 'accessibility', 'interoperability', and the 'reuse' (Stall et al., 2019; Wilkinson et al., 2016). First, metadata and data must be easy to find by individuals and computers for (automatic) discovery, alias 'findable' (Weigel et al., 2020). Second, the 'accessibility' of research data must be provided. Users need to know how to get access to the data possibly including authentication and authorization (Allcock et al., 2019). Third, research data must be integrable with other data as well as 'interoperable' with analysis applications and workflows (Reiser et al., 2018) Fourth, the ultimate goal of the guiding principles is to optimize the 'reuse' of data. Therefore, data and metadata must be well described to replicate and combine them in different settings (Magagna et al., 2020). Based on the FAIR data principles, Bishop et al. (2019) analyze science data reusers' information-seeking behavior to determine fitness for use to determine how researchers define and assess product quality and compatibility based on a FAIR framework.

2.1.4 Contribution: Researchers and data reuse

Research has focused on the motivations underlying data reuse. However, research on the different aspects based on the FAIR principles is quite sparse (exceptions include e.g. Bishop et al. (2019)). Therefore, the following questions arise: *What aspects of findability do researchers value? More specifically, how do researchers find data and which challenges do they face? What challenges related to accessibility and interoperability do researchers face? What are the main aspects based on the acceptance of technologies (UTAUT model) that lead to a decision to reuse data?* To answer these questions, we conducted a qualitative and quantitative analysis. Based on the FAIR framework, we carry out 14 interviews with researchers of different disciplines to understand how they navigate data reuse based on the FAIR principles. The quantitative survey heavily draws on Curty (2015) and Prandner and Hasen-gruber (2021). We asked participants to rank the importance of different types of data, different sources for obtaining data, different tools when searching for data, factors that affect their reuse, familiarity with FAIR principles, reusability based on

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data FAIRness, and different attitudes towards the reuse of data. We also draw on the UTAUT model to explain how researchers' attitudes affect their reuse behavior. Both the UTAUT model and the FAIR approach contribute to the research on data reuse.

3 Qualitative Interviews

3.1 Methods

The research question for the qualitative interviews are guided by the following question: *what characteristics do researchers value when reusing data?* More specifically, we are interested in the aspects that can be incorporated during the technical implementation of EOSC. For instance, we aim at understanding which problems researchers face when accessing data given that experts are currently working on technical aspects of access control.

In order to answer these questions, we conducted semi-structured interviews. To recreate the atmosphere of a face-to-face interview as closely as possible, we asked participants to use a webcam during the interview. For further analysis we recorded the interview and transcribed them. We asked participants to sign a consent form as precondition for participating (available at the repository). The questionnaire is available at [AUSSDA](#).

We determined which characteristics our sample should fulfill to provide the most valuable insights into our research question. We selected respondents based on the following criteria: researchers that reuse data for research, different scientific disciplines, location, career stage, researchers who work at universities or research institutes. We also took gender into account and relation to EOSC-activities.

We only invited researchers who have already considered reusing data for their research. Researchers did not necessarily have to complete this endeavour, but we excluded researchers who categorically rejected the idea of reusing data as we are interested in the specific aspects of reusing data (and not the motivation for reusing data). We sampled researchers according to their **scientific disciplines** using the OECD (2007) criteria: Natural sciences, Engineering and technology, Medical and health sciences, Agricultural sciences, Social sciences and Humanities. In the first research cycle, we interviewed one researcher of each of these six disciplines. In the following research cycles, we incorporated the sub-categories. For instance, if a researcher from the first research cycle representing natural sciences is active in physical sciences, the researcher representing natural sciences in the second research cycle ideally works in a different sub-field, e.g. mathematics. We aimed at including as many sub-disciplines as possible to diversify the views on data reuse, but due

to the small sample, were able to cover sub-disciplines. In addition, we selected researchers based on their work place in one of the five EOSC-Pillar **countries** (Austria, Belgium, Germany, France, Italy).

Our sampling strategy regarding countries was twofold: On the one hand, we aimed at including researchers from all countries. On the other hand, we acknowledged the different size of the countries by inviting more researchers from the three larger countries. In addition, we took differences within countries into account by selecting researchers from different organizations. As researchers in different **career stages** may have different perceptions, we took the following career stages into account: PhD students, post-doctoral researchers and tenured professors. The ratio of these categories in our sample should approximately reflect the distribution in reality, hence, more PhD students than post-doctoral researchers and more post-doctoral researchers than tenured professors. We only included researchers who mainly work for universities or research institutes that do not primarily pursue commercial interests. In other words, we excluded researchers who exclusively work for private organizations that pursue commercial interests. We took the **gender** of researchers into account when drawing the sample in order to ensure the representation of women. The distribution of women approximately followed the actual distribution of women in the scientific disciplines. As the distribution of women certainly differs across disciplines and career stages, men are most likely over-represented in the sample. In order to get a fresh perspective, we primarily invited researchers who did not contribute to open science or EOSC.

3.2 Qualitative Results

This section presents the main findings of our qualitative interviews. As mentioned in the [methods section](#), the qualitative interviews were guided by the overarching question of how EOSC can facilitate the reuse of data amongst researchers. The main research question was: *what characteristics do researchers value when reusing data?* More specifically, the interviews focused on aspects that could be taken into account during the technical implementation of EOSC. Therefore, we tried to uncover the problems researchers face when accessing research data considering that experts are currently working on technical aspects of access control. The key aspects we investigated are based on the FAIR principles. We conducted a total of 14 interviews with researchers from different disciplines and sub-disciplines. The disciplines included natural sciences (5), social sciences (3), agricultural science (1), humanities (1), medical and health science (2), engineering and technology (2). We describe the main findings by outlining the main points mentioned across interviews and citing specific quotations throughout the text. The analysis was conducted as follows: first, the interviews were read through and sorted by codes. For each code, we chose specific quotes based on the FAIR principles.

3.2.1 Findability

This section focuses on the following questions: *How do researchers search for reusable data? What technical features may help researchers to find data?* Given the diversity of disciplines, the types and sources of data varied. Nonetheless, despite variability in the responses, the interviews pointed to common approaches and challenges when searching for data. Of all sources mentioned by the researchers, digital portals were the most prevalent. Seven of the 14 interviewees mentioned digital portals or websites, and six of them pointed to specific portals they rely on in their discipline or field (e.g. NOW for paleontology or CEMEX for atmospheric sciences). These answers were straight-forward, as Interview 3 exemplifies: “I find the data that I need to analyze generally from the CEMEX portal. The CEMEX [...] is the main portal that I refer to when I need to fetch some modelled outputs” (Interview 3 2021). Five of the 14 interviews mentioned networks/networking or partnerships, as well as publications as a main source for finding data. As Interviewee 5 explained: “It’s [...] basically using my already established networks to find data” (Interview 5 2021). Four of the 14 interviewees mentioned search engines (three specifically mentioned Google, and three mentioned additional search engines (e.g. Web of Science or Scopus). As one researcher mentioned, Google is playing an increasingly relevant role compared to other search engines. “[...] you have Web of Science [...] in the meantime it’s Google Scholar [...] replacing it, but I think more and more you also just do a simple search on Google [...]” (Interview 10 2021). Interviewee 1 also largely mentioned search engines: “I would start with a Google search [...] type in the variable [...] then I search for publications[...] and for searching publications

I would use [...] typical search engines like Web of Science, Scopus [...] Google Scholar” (Interview 1 2021). Two of the 14 researchers mentioned direct contact with authors, public databases, university repositories, or other third-party sources. One researcher named their own project as their main source for data (material science), while another named a specific metadata catalogue (digital humanities). The interviewees relied on one or two of the latter approaches, and some recurred to several of these approaches/sources when searching for data. Overall, the interviewees mentioned an average of 2 main data sources. Interviewee 2 outlined a multifaceted approach to searching for data by turning to institutions, data repositories, and publications presenting new datasets: “My first reflex is to go into that list of the available datasets and look whether the data I am looking for is available. I also go to big institutions [...] scientific associations are a good source for new datasets [...], but also repositories [...]. Either at national levels [...] or university repositories for instance Harvard has a new dataverse repository where a lot of colleagues put their new datasets available [...] Or there is also a number of journals that are publishing short articles that are presenting new datasets that are available and so I am also following that[...].” (Interview 2 2021).

The quotes underscored the main approaches regarding how researchers search for data. The researchers we interviewed had a diverse range of approaches when it comes to searching for data including data repositories, publications, researchers within their networks, events such as conferences, or simple google searches. As outlined previously, three of the interviewees mentioned google as a main go-to point rather than other web engines or repositories given the simplicity of finding up-to-date publications and data. Nonetheless, researchers face challenges related to findability of data in searchable resources with clear and explicit metadata that provides crucial information about the data to the researcher.

Regarding the main challenges that researchers face, four of the 14 researchers mentioned the difficulty of finding non-digitalized data. As Interview 1 mentioned: “I often encounter the situation that I know that the data is available or is, at least the data exists, but then it is often tricky to actually find the place to actually download a certain data or to get a clear information whether the data can be downloaded or shared or not” (Interview 1 2021). Three of the 14 researchers mentioned the willingness to share data as a main challenge in their field. As Interviewee 15 said: “Researchers, maybe even more so in the qualitative field, consider the data like their personal achievement to have it collected, and are quite hesitant to share, especially when it’s beyond their personal networks. [...] it makes it harder to convince scientists to share the data for a secondary use” (Interview 15 2021). Three of the 14 researchers also mentioned the clear overview of data as a main challenge - even when repositories exist, they are often unorganized or there are too many of them so that the data is not comprehensive or centrally located. Interviewee 5 summed this up: “Currently, GitHub, GitLab [...] is an unorganized [...] there is no global overview” (Interview 5 2021). Two of the 14 researchers mentioned the sensitivity

of data and privacy laws as a barrier to finding certain types of data. As Interviewee 11 put it; “[...] the mortality and health data [...] are covered by privacy [...] and this is probably a European law”.

One of the main difficulties mentioned in the interviews was the lack of centralization and organization of the repositories. 10 total mentions in 7 of the interviews showed that researchers lack centralized, global repositories that contain more data regarding their quantity and scope. Interviewee 9 summed this up: “The problem is that there are too many, and they are all incomplete. We need to merge the different sources” (Interviewee 9 2021). A further challenge cited was verifying whether data from scientific papers are applicable to the researchers’ research question. Specifically, the interviewees outlined the challenge of verifying its reliability and applicability in a quick and efficient manner. As Interviewee 8 indicated: “[...] it takes a lot of time to verify if they are applicable to what we do and if we can accept the data. Because [...] in our line of work it poses some risk to use data from unknown sources” (Interview 8 2021).

In the face of these challenges, the following quotes underscored some of the researchers wishes that would facilitate the process of finding data. Of the 14 interviews, 10 researchers mentioned tools that could improve data findability. The responses include solutions such as a global overview of data, more centralized data repositories. Seven of the 14 interviews pointed to better, universal, comprehensive repositories/platforms. As Interviewee 2 said: “I think a one-point entry would be great. And right now, Harvard has a lead with that. You see that their dataverse platform is quite heavily used. It’s great but on the other hand I think the European science community could do better” (Interview 2 2021). Two researchers mentioned machine learning as a tool to make finding specific datasets and variables easy (e.g. by predicting labels). Interviewee 13 specified: “[...] it would be helpful if there are appropriate algorithms, machine learning algorithms, deep learning algorithms that would facilitate the use of big data” (Interview 13 2021). Interviewee 11 pointed to the lack of finding local data: “from the national point of view, [it would be useful] to have a website dedicated for all the datasets that are available at the local scale. So let’s say urban or municipal” (Interview 11 2021). For Interviewee 9, this also implied improving web design to easily identify and find the data they are looking for: “Web design [...] I know that the information is there most of the time. It is just that sometimes you don’t read carefully enough or you don’t see the button which is explaining that this is this or this” (Interview 9 2021). Interviewee 2 stressed a European-level transdisciplinary repository as a helpful tool: “Having a common repository would be great, either of course at the country levels, but a lot of countries are not doing that yet, or at the European level [...]” (Interviewee 2 2021). Interviewee 5 mentioned a data catalogue: “Something like a data catalogue would be nice, where you can have like a general overview of what you’re looking for [...] that would be also very useful for software” (Interviewee 5 2021). Interviewee 14 referred to the importance of finding a way to link data based on clear vocabularies /

labels: “If you wanted to use multiple data sets together it could be tricky because, maybe sometimes you have some link between them, but it’s not really explained or it’s not connected [...]” (Interviewee 14 2021).

The previous quotes revealed some of the main challenges and possible tools to facilitate finding data for reuse. However, interviewees from certain disciplines faced more difficulties than others. In paleontology, Interviewee 7 underscored the difficulty of finding data in this field and the importance of expanding networks and sorting through the data in the following quote: “Sometimes it’s difficult to find the actual material, because it’s published, maybe even with pictures, and the institution does not exist anymore. So the collection was moved from here to there, maybe during the war, maybe later on [...]” (Interview 7 2021).

Overall, regarding findability, researchers pointed to similar approaches when searching for reusable data, but they still varied depending on the specific task at hand. Some interviewees outlined more multifaceted options/approaches to finding data ranging from networks to publications, data repositories and data made available by public institutions, while other interviewees highlighted one or two main approaches such as focusing solely on networks, publications, or search engines. Similarly, several interviewees spoke of data repositories more generally, while others mentioned one or two specific repositories prevalent in their discipline. Moreover, the interviewees underscored similar challenges when looking for data related to easily searchable resources with the necessary metadata: the lack of centralized repositories or data catalogues, and the challenge of finding the precise data related to a specific research question. The discipline-specific character of some of the repositories and the lack of cohesion even within disciplines (i.e. several different repositories with different data available) was also a prevalent theme. Regarding which technical features might help, one of the interviewees mentioned algorithms or increasing the use of machine learning to increase findability.

3.2.2 Key findings about findability

Key findings

- Across disciplines, the interviewees strategies regarding finding data varied greatly. Researchers in disciplines that rely on readily available datasets containing qualitative or quantitative data have a broader scope of strategies and options when it comes findability. The main strategies mentioned were networks, publications, data repositories, search engines, and public institutions.
- Researchers from disciplines that study other types of material such as objects (i.e. paleontology) had a more narrow approach to finding data and face more difficulties locating and studying the material. According to the interviewees, centralized repositories containing the location and images or scans of the objects are underdeveloped.
- One of the main challenges faced by researchers is twofold and includes 1) the lack of central repositories at a more aggregated level (i.e. at the national level) or 2) more cross-discipline central data catalogues or repositories across disciplines.
- Pointing to the heterogenous character of the repositories or the lack of an efficient overview and metadata when searching for data, researchers stressed that it is often easier and more efficient to use a search engine such as google rather than find the data via repositories.
- Researchers mentioned algorithms and machine learning as a searching tool for specific datasets or variables. Overall, increasing automatization instead of manually searching across (often incomplete) repositories was mentioned to be helpful.

3.2.3 Accessibility

In this section, we aim to uncover *which features and legal frameworks might help researchers in accessing datasets*. The section outlines some of the main challenges expressed by the interviewees when accessing data and potentially helpful tools that would facilitate data accessibility. Many of the difficulties and potential tools were closely intertwined with some of the aspects of findability discussed in the previous section or interoperability ([see next section](#)).

Overall, the main challenges mentioned regarding accessibility encompassed several themes. The researchers mentioned an average of three main difficulties. Four of the 14 interviewees mentioned the lack of data sharing as a barrier to accessing data. As Interviewee 7 explained: “if you want data from other research groups where

you have maybe some interest but you are not a colleague, not a member of the group [...] sometimes they are very closed and don't want to share data" (Interview 7 2021). Three of the 14 interviewees mentioned data moratoriums and the fact that access is often restricted for a specific period of time as a challenge to quick, uncomplicated access to data. For instance, Interviewee 13 said: "the data is on a moratorium because the paper has not been published and then you basically have to wait before you can use it [...] which is also one of the reasons why we are not using their database very often" (Interview 13 2021). Three of the 14 interviews also mentioned the data management as a barrier to accessing data. As Interviewee 2 expressed: "sometimes data is available on a website but you cannot necessarily extract all of the data sets, so it's really about the easiness of managing the data" (Interview 2 2021). More specifically, 5 of the 14 researchers underscored the quality of the code/format or incomplete documentation that would allow for efficient access to data. As Interviewee 11 stressed: "you have to have a really specific skill in order to elaborate the data. And if you don't have it, you need a lot of time in order to understand how to write the script, or how to elaborate those data [...] it's really lucky that they are there, and that they are freely downloadable, but at the same time, it's not so easy to manage them" (Interview 11 2021). Interviewee 1 summed it up as follows: "a major obstacle are the data formats [...] sometimes a dataset is available, so there is a physical file somewhere on a website and I can download this file and I store it on my computer, but I don't have the necessary metainformation to actually open the file and understand its content [...] the description of the dataset itself is also critical" (Interview 1 2021).

Four of the 14 interviews mentioned data availability as one of the main challenges to accessing data. Interviewee 2 described this as follows: "Sometimes it's the data availability because you know that a project is undergoing or complete, but the data is not made available [...] you might have to wait a couple of years before you can get a hand on the data" (Interview 2 2021). Four of the interviewees mentioned legal issues as a challenge when accessing data, such as license agreements. For instance, Interview 8 said: "I need to look at the license they offer [...] they might have restrictions on reusing the source code [...] which means that I have to include a legal notice in my software [...]" (Interview 8 2021). Interviewee 5 also referred to legal issues related to licensing: "Assume I want to integrate a certain subpackage into our software [...] we can't do that if it's under a different license [...] sometimes involved in projects where the data or the software is under non-disclosure agreement (NDA), so that is of course also an issue because you cannot write publications or anything" (Interview 5 2021). Another legal aspect encompassed the transnational sharing of data. Interviewee 4 described this as follows: "The other aspect that I think is important for my work are legal concerns. For instance, a particular country might not be willing to share their information they have collected about their own forests [...]" (Interview 4 2021). Three of the interviews mentioned data access as a very time-consuming process that could be done much more efficiently. Interviewee 9 summed it up: "The second difficulty [...] when need to fill forms which are very

long, very detailed, to access the data [...] it's often a waste of time [...] And then we have forms to create accounts and so on to access to the data" (Interview 9 2021). Another interviewee mentioned the lack of persistent URLs. Interviewee 5 described this as follows: "data that we are accessing is usually software, that is Github repos or Gitlab repos or some kind of a Git repos, and what can happen there is that the URLs are not persistent, so you find something in a paper and you try to access the code, or the software and it is not there anymore. So that is an issue" (Interview 5 2021). Last, two of the 14 interviewees stressed the challenge of being able to contact the data producers years after the data was produced. As Interviewee 13 described: "you always have the possibility to write an email to the person, of course this is difficult if it was a PhD student or Post Doc that now started working in the industry and is gone, so yeah, hopefully then the group or the institute has an administrator that could answer your question but this is really a lot of personal interaction for like specific questions" (Interview 13 2021).

In sum, the interviews highlighted several issues hindering accessibility. The main issues included data availability, the gap between available versions of the dataset and the actual data used in the publication. Data moratoriums and bureaucratic issues are an additional barrier when accessing data. Furthermore, the extensive and time-consuming nature of the login/sign-up process and permission is a further hindrance; the vast amount of log-ins and passwords necessary for all of the different repositories and the long and detailed access forms. Another issue was the lacking data management and incomplete supplementary material and documentation. In the face of these challenges, some of the researchers emphasized possible tools to improve data accessibility. Overall, four of the 14 researchers mentioned better platforms. Specifically, they emphasized the use of a single id for all platforms to facilitate the log-in an access. This underscores the importance of centralized repositories that was mentioned [in the previous section](#). Examples included a centralized web page or repository where researchers can enter interests and automatically receive a list of relevant databases (Interviews 9 and 11) or a single ID to access all the different platforms and data repositories to avoid the cumbersome process of creating logins and filling out access forms for each database. Researcher 9 summarizes this point as follows: "Clearly it would be very interesting if we have a kind of general ID or identification. [...] I know that there are different IDs which are shared by different applications. It would be easier if we can use kind of single IDs for all these platforms [...]" (Interview 9 2021). Otherwise, there were mainly single mentions of specific issues: increased data sharing (Interview 15 2021), artificial intelligence (Interview 14 2021), increased transparency (Interview 1), contact with data producers (Interview 10), and persistent identifiers (Interview 5).

3.2.4 Key findings about accessibility

Key findings

- Researchers pointed out similar difficulties regarding the accessibility of data for reuse. A main barrier mentioned across the board was the creation of several different accounts and passwords for several different websites.
- A further issue encompasses the (1) lack of continuity or accessibility of metadata when the data are no longer available, (2) being able to access data when the URLs or identifiers are not persistent and data cannot be accessed, or (3) contacting researchers that are responsible for the data that are no longer in academia.
- Legal barriers or licensing issues were mentioned by some of the researchers as a main reason for not accessing or reusing data. These pertained to using software, implying inclusion of a legal notice, but also data which is not allowed to be shared or data that has been blocked for a specific amount of time before reusing.
- Another substantive challenge was the access to the actual data used in a given publication including the codes and documentation. Researchers spend a large amount of time sorting out the gaps between code, software and documentation.
- The researchers interviewed mentioned several potential solutions that involve minimizing or reducing the number of single IDs for all of the different platforms and optimizing efficiency when accessing a large amount of datasets.

3.2.5 Interoperability

This section focuses on *the difficulties that researchers encounter concerning the format or structure of files and which features prove helpful*. Nine of 14 interviewees mentioned several challenges regarding interoperability, while 5 of the 14 interviewees do not face challenges or did not mention specific challenges. The main challenges covered the following topics, which are intertwined with issues of findability and accessibility: deficient documentation, lack of standardized coding, the data format that hinders efficient merging, and the time-consuming process of getting the data into the necessary format. Specifically, a main challenge is the lack of cohesiveness between files made available and the necessary accompanying documentation/auxiliary files, which makes merging datasets much more difficult. Interviewee 1 pinpointed missing documentation and errors as the main challenges that hinder interoperability: “I have encountered difficulties and they most relate

to missing documentation or simply errors in the dataset” (Interview 1 2021). Interviewee 14 summarized the importance of common vocabulary and structure in the datasets: “having good ontologies and structured data is very important [...] at least using a common vocabulary of what it contains and then if we would connect with each other, that could really help in searching for it and also making it interoperable” (Interview 14 2021). Five of the 14 interviewees pointed to the difficulties of obtaining a comprehensive description of the dataset in a common language/code and with complete documentation. Interview 13 said: “There are million ways to write code to get to the same result or answer or way to solve the problem, so coding is a very individual thing I would say and if it’s not well documented then that might cause a problem also in optimizing it [interoperability]” (Interview 13 2021).

Another challenge for interoperability mentioned by 6 of the 14 interviews are the data formats. Interview 1 summarized the challenge: “Yes, a major obstacle are the data formats [...] sometimes a dataset is available [...] but I don’t have the necessary metainformation to actually open the file and understand its content [...] the description of the dataset itself is also critical” (Interview 1 2021). Three of the 14 interviewees emphasized the amount of time that goes into putting the data into the correct format in order to make it interoperable. As Interviewee 13 says, “The solution here was to lose a lot of time and study and trying to write a good script [...] it is not easy at the beginning, especially when you’re programming [...] it takes a lot of time ” (Interview 13 2021). Interviewee 14 also mentioned this challenge: “always there will be some custom parsing that goes on [...] for some data sets it’s even too complicated and then you spend a lot of time doing this parsing” (Interview 14 2021). Interviewee 9 stressed the challenge of working in interdisciplinary teams since researchers across disciplines have different ways of dealing with data and also deal with different data formats. Last, Interviewee 5 mentioned the issue of software. “Having an interoperable software is like a very big effort, a challenge. It starts with compilers, with libraries that you link [...] then you have incompatible or interoperability issues. Then you have problems with programming language” (Interview 5 2021).

For other interviewees, interoperability was not a problem. One of the researchers (Interviewee 15) works mainly with qualitative data and mentioned the easiness of merging and integrating data since it is the same type of data. Interviewee 15 summarized the process as follows: “As it is mainly text documents I have been working on, it has been fairly easy to process and work with the data I am reusing [...] and even integrate it with other sources of data or with data I have collected” (Interview 15 2021). Interoperability was also not an issue for Interviewee 8, who worked mainly with numerical data. However, despite similar formats, Interviewee 8 stressed the importance of documentation: “Some formats allow for accessing data very easily. [...] even then it could be helpful to have a document, documentation that describes what you can find in this dataset. If it’s binary or just numeric format, just numbers, it’s even more important to have documentation or better if you

have a toolkit, software toolkit that can read and manipulate the data. Or filter it” (Interview 8 2021). Integrating data was mainly a problem when using different types of data, as Interviewee 11 said: “Now climate date is in a format, the date of the health dataset is in another one. [...] then if you have to merge it, you merge it by date, and if the format is not the same, it gave zero as an output. So it takes also two days in order to understand [...] if the date is the problem, how can I change the format?” (Interview 11 2021)

The interviewees were also asked which kind of tools would facilitate integrating and merging different datasets. Three of the 14 interviewees highlighted the importance of a common type of coding scheme, common vocabulary, and the quality of scripts made available to researchers. For instance, Interviewee 14 stressed “I would say all this knowledge that I have cited is more promising like, having good ontologies and structured data is very important [...] At least describe using a common vocabulary what it contains and then if we would connect with each other, that could really help in searching for it and also making it interoperable” (Interview 14 2021). Similarly, Interviewee 2 concurred regarding the importance of common codes in the scientific community and summed up many of the issues that were pointed out.

[...] one thing that could be very useful is standardized ways to merge datasets, in a sense that sometimes you work on countries or parties and you might have general codes that the scientific community agrees on, so that you can then merge datasets for various sources in a much easier way [...] I think that’s also how you can improve scientific knowledge is to take data from various sources and merge them so that you can conduct new original analyses, but the merging of datasets is something that can take quite a long time and a lot of effort because there is again no real standardized ways to code units of analysis or actors and that could potentially be a help (Interviewee 2 2021).

Three of the 14 interviews referred to online tools as supportive regarding the interoperability between datasets and converting data. As Interviewee 3 said: “Some websites, they provide their own remote tools to combine data. That would be really helpful sometimes...those are services that you can do remotely” (Interview 3 2021). Another researcher referred to Python tools: “I have Python tools or command line tools out there that can do the job for you” (Interview 4 2021). However even the use of these online tools require additional commands or additional work to achieve the desired result. One researcher mentioned machine learning, while another researcher emphasized the software side of interoperability as a crucial tool (see Interview 14).

Overall, the main challenges lie in the lack of standardized coding in the scientific community, and the compatibility of the software researchers use and the approach to making data available to other researchers. Specifically, the interviews emphasized the following aspects: (1) how datasets are described and the availability of a comprehensive supporting documentation, the (2) codes and a sufficient explanation thereof, and the (3) availability of different formats so that researchers can quickly use the format they need. Despite such challenges, the interviewees men-

tioned several different tools/conditions that facilitate the interoperability between data sources. However as the interviewees outlined above, it often comes down to adequate documentation and metadata. One interviewee pointed to the necessity of developing research software in Europe in a similar way as it is being developed in the US and consolidating the license landscape, drawing on tools such as machine learning in order to predict similarities between datasets. Interviewee 5 indicated the necessity of investing into research software development:

There are strong efforts trying to improve the interoperability and they are not necessarily in Europe but more in the US. The US are probably quite a bit ahead of Europe in terms of identifying research software as a very important asset [...] under Barack Obama [...] they had an executive order of 3.4 billion, and half of that money goes into research software development [...] a good fraction of that is looking into interoperability. So you have a lot of packages out there, and you would be much more efficient if these packages could all work together. And that requires of course adapting and integrating, but this also requires consolidating the license landscape I would say (Interviewee 5 2021).

3.2.6 Key findings about interoperability

Key findings

- Challenges regarding interoperability varied across disciplines. Researchers working with different types of data or interdisciplinary teams had more issues than researchers that use only qualitative or quantitative data.
- The main challenge facing researchers regarding interoperability and integrating data from different sources was the lack of cohesiveness in the files made available and a lack of a comprehensive description of the datasets and/or accompanying documentation (i.e. high quality scripts) made available for data reuse.
- According to the interviewees, the lack of a standardized approach in the scientific community regarding coding results in the researcher spending a lot of time and effort in order to format the data that will fit to their usage. Their suggestions for improvement included using a common vocabulary or a standardized approach when providing scripts.
- Another major obstacle related to the last two points are the data formats. Researchers might be able to access the data, yet are unable to use it because they lack the necessary metainformation to open the file or understand the content of the latter.
- Last, researchers point to the issue of software. The researchers admitted that they write their own format within the software they work in as different softwares use different codes.
- The interviewees recommended investing more money into software development in order to integrate and consolidate the research landscape and investing into tools like machine learning that can help predict some of the content of data that would make linking them to another easier.

3.2.7 Reusability

The last section of our interview asks researchers (1) *how they decide whether or not to reuse given data when they have found it* and (2) *which information researchers require for making this decision*. Last, (3) *which technical features may facilitate this decision and which legal concerns do researchers have concerning the reuse of data?*

Based on the interviews, the main factors determining researchers' data reuse included the role of good metadata, the credibility of the data, the relevance to the

research question, the data structure or format, data management, the presentation of the datasets, and the license model. Overall, the interviewees mentioned an average of two factors that affect whether they reuse data. Again, many of the factors are interrelated. Six of the 14 interviewees emphasized the importance of good documentation and metadata. As Interviewee 13 outlined, “Having more metadata would certainly facilitate the decision, because the more information you have the better you can decide” (Interview 13 2021). Interviewee 11 gave an explanation as to why metadata is so important: “Because you have the script and you have the dataset, you can see exactly what they did and follow the path” (Interview 11 2021). Interviewee 1 summed it up: “It’s really critical to have a good data documentation. So, I have to know how this dataset was produced, under which assumptions, who did it, was it evaluated, was it tested [...] , was it published and what are the conditions to use this dataset [...] the more information I have here, the more likely it is that I use a certain dataset” (Interview 1 2021).

Six of the 14 interviewees mentioned overall credibility of the dataset as an additional important factor. Credibility included issues such as being able to reproduce and verify the data and overall reliability of the latter. As Interview 8 put it: “all data should be reproducible and there should be enough information provided alongside the data such that it is reproducible” (Interview 8 2021). Credibility is also related to the data source, which was mentioned by three interviewees. Again, Interviewee 8 underscored the importance of the source: “I would say the most important factor for me would be the source of the data. If [...] this is a respectable or [...] reliable institution, that should be enough” (Interview 8 2021). Relatedly, a scientific publication accompanying the data is another main aspect of data reuse. According to Interviewee 3, “The presence of a publication, of scientific publication behind this data, it makes this data more reliable [...] sometimes, it is essential that somebody else has validated this data [...]” (Interview 3 2021) . Three of the 14 interviewees also explicitly mentioned data quality. Interviewee 2 described quality as the overarching factor affecting their data reuse: “Quality of course [...] for that, you need as much information on the dataset or the survey as possible[...] all the information about the data gathering process, a clear codebook and a good quality of the data” (Interview 2 2021). In this vein, Interviewee 1 highlighted the role of transparency: “I guess the more transparent the data producers are, I think the more willing I would be to use, to reuse this dataset” (Interview 1 2021). The remaining factors included 1) data structure, 2) data management, and 3) the presentation of datasets on the webpages. Each of these factors was mentioned by 2 interviewees.

Legal issues were mentioned by most interviewees when asked how they affect their decision to reuse data. Eleven of the 14 interviewees mentioned that legal issues are a barrier when reusing data. License models were mentioned by 4 of the 14 interviewees as the main factor affecting data reuse. As Interviewee 8 put it, “[...] you can not reuse data without the correct license. I am not familiar too much what licenses are available for data. I think all of the data that I use or we use is

basically openly available” (Interview 8 2021). Interviewee 4 underscored the license model as a determinant of data reuse: “every library has their own contracts, their own licensing models, their own usage rights, and sometimes it can become really really difficult to understand what you can reuse and how you can reuse it” (Interview 4 2021). Further issues affecting that were mentioned by interviewees included (1) the anonymization of data (Interview 15), (2) the handling of sensitive data (Interview 11), (3) transnational agreements (Interviews 1, 8 and 13). Regarding the anonymization of data, Interviewee 15 stated, “especially in the political field, the problem of anonymization is, is key [...] I can imagine a lot of situations or cases where a reliable anonymization would render the data almost worthless” (Interview 15 2021). Dealing with sensitive data is a further challenge when deciding to reuse data. Interview 11 said, “the mortality dataset related to socioeconomic factors. There are a lot of legal boundaries that I have to follow [...] which is the line between publishable or not publishable” (Interview 11 2021). Interviewee 13 mentioned international protocol, which implies requesting permission from authorities. When reusing data, Interviewee 13 states that “this is certainly a legal issue which we are facing at the moment when using data which is not our own and where we can’t be certain [whether the data followed the protocol]” (Interview 13 2021). In a similar vein, Interviewee 8 outlines the role of NDAs when using specific data from the United States: “We work together with other space agencies and if they provide to us data which is based on the rockets, for example, NASA does this, the Americans have this International Traffic in Arms Regulation (ITAR) which forces us to treat this data with care and to make sure that [...] we don’t share it with people who haven’t signed such NDAs [...]” (Interview 8 2021).

The researchers were asked if they were familiar with EOSC. Six out of fourteen had heard of it but only had a vague idea of what it was. Seven of fourteen had never heard of it, and one did not respond to this question. One interviewee said, “I do know very little, I do know that some people in this institution where I am working are actually involved in that, and I do know that the idea is to create something like a database across all Europe where data is shared, and that they are also creating infrastructure to store the data, that’s about all I know” (Interview 5). Another interviewee expressed unfamiliarity regarding EOSC: “I’ve heard of it but to be honest I would not know what it’s for or how I could use it, so I would need to look into it” (Interview 13).

As the previous quotes from the interviews underscored, there are many different factors that go into deciding to reuse data including the quality of the data, the source, the publications, and the legal issues related to the data. Some incentives mentioned in the interviews could potentially increase data reuse/data sharing. Five of the 14 interviewees mentioned issues regarding incentives to increase data sharing (which would affect reuse). For instance, Interviewee 5 highlighted the importance of funding agencies to identify the potential that lies in the data and require projects to be published under FAIR principles: “I think it’s important [...] for the funding

agencies to identify the potential that lies in the data [...] I would like to see a push from the funding agencies that they actually require for projects that are funded that all the data has to be published under the FAIR principles (Interview 5 2021)”. Interviewee 1 mentioned that researchers want to be acknowledged for sharing their data, and that a publication in a journal or even on data repositories can increase visibility of the researcher and the data: “[...] I think people are willing to share a dataset that is associated with a publication, because they get citation for this publication and this way they get credits from people using their data” (Interview 1 2021). Another point regarding data reuse involved the data production side. Interviewee 2 stressed the necessity of training and information in the management of their own data, i.e. the necessary steps, how to create a DOI, where to deposit the data and how to make it available. They sum it up as follows: “[...] I think we are not always aware or trained in terms of, how do you deal with data ownership, how do you deal with all that [...] and I think there this some training and information necessary for the scientific community in the management of their own data” (Interview 2 2021).

3.2.8 Key findings about reusability

Key findings

- The main factors in determining data reuse included the (1) quality of the data, the (2) role of good data documentation and metadata, the (3) source of the data, the (4) publication of the data, (5) overall transparency by the data producers and reliability of the data, and (6) and relevance of the data. These answers are in line with the literature showing that perceived efficacy and efficiency of data reuse are strong predictors of reuse behavior [Curty \(2017\)](#).
- Legal barriers/challenges mentioned in the interviews regarding data reuse or making data available for reuse included data anonymization, sensitive data handling, whether international agreements, and data licensing.
- The interviews mentioned the lack of data sharing/publication for reuse trace back to data producers. According to the interviewees, data producers seek credit for sharing data, however giving adequate credit to the data producers is not that common.
- One interview pointed out the lack of data reuse can also be traced back to the institutional level. For instance, funding agencies play a central role in whether data is reused or not.

4 Quantitative Survey

4.1 Methods

We carried out a quantitative survey to find out more specifics about researchers' data reuse. The questionnaire and data are available at [AUSSDA](#). The quantitative survey encompasses researchers' views on 1) the importance of different kinds of data reuse and reuse, 2) the importance of different tools for finding data, and the main aspects influencing whether a researcher reuses data or not, 3) whether reuse is encouraged, and 4) perspectives on different aspects of reusability. The survey also asks how important different services are, how available they are, the relevance of international collaboration and factors that influence data sharing along with potential services that might help with research.

We generated five separate links for each country and distributed them in each country. Our field period began mid-October 2021 and ended on December 3rd, 2021. Due to differing legal frameworks, the survey dissemination procedure differed by institution. For the University of Vienna, directly contacting researchers via e-mail was not possible due to legal restrictions. Instead, we sent the survey link via the Rectorate's monthly newsletter. Since the response rate was quite low (<30), the Rectorate sent the survey link directly to the faculty deans to forward to the researchers. In Belgium we followed a similar procedure; the survey was disseminated via newsletter. Similar to Austria, the response rate was extremely low (<5), but we did not have the possibility of increasing our response rate. In France, the survey was disseminated via newsletters or mailing lists associated with INSERM, IFREMER, and INSU/CNRS. In Italy, a similar procedure was followed. The survey was disseminated via mailing lists associated with CNR and INAF. In Germany, researchers from four universities in Baden-Württemberg were contacted directly by e-mail.

Table 4.1 summarizes the approach for each institution. Although the emails were sent to employees, we filtered them and include only researchers. The survey was designed to garner a complete sample of researchers that we contacted within each specific University or Researcher Network. The total number of observations in the dataset after completion of the field period was 926, including participants that only clicked on the link without actually responding to any survey questions. Out of the 926, a total of 592 respondents reached the last page and submitted the survey. We

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got over 100 responses for all countries except for Belgium, where four respondents clicked on the survey but only two of them completed it. In Austria, 191 clicked on the survey, however only 120 made it to the last page of the survey. In Germany, 226 clicked on the survey and 146 reached the last page. In France, 276 people clicked on the survey and 163 reached the last page. In Italy, the numbers were 229 and 161, respectively. Although we did not reach all of the researchers we aimed for and the data may not be representative of the entire research community, we do have a large amount of completed surveys (592) which provide us some insight into the researchers' views on data reuse and related topics.

University	Method	Field period	# targeted	Reminders
DE: Freiburg	E-mail	22.10-03.12	2023 Employees	yes
DE: Hohenheim	E-mail	22.10-03.12	535 Employees	yes
DE: Ulm	E-mail	22.10-03.12	1633 Employees	yes
DE: Heidelberg	E-mail	22.10-03.12	1168 Employees	yes
AT: Vienna	Newsletter E-mail (Deans)	13.10-03.12	7364 Researchers	no
BE: Ghent	Newsletter	13.10-03.12	13701 Researchers	no
FR: IFREMER	E-mail	08.10-03.12	519 Researchers	no
FR: INSERM	Mailing list	08.10-03.12	1101 Researchers	yes
FR: INSU/CNRS	E-mail	15.11-03.12	3327 Researchers	yes
IT:CNR	Mailing list	08.10-03.12	4800 Researchers	yes
IT: INAF	Mailing list	08.10-03.12	Not available	yes

The following figures provide an overview of the respondents' characteristics. Figure 4.1 shows the share of respondents by institution. We received the highest number of responses from CNR in Italy, the University of Vienna, and INSERM in France. The least amount of responses stem from Ghent University in Belgium, CNRS in France, and Hohenheim in Germany. There were no responses from the University of Ulm due to spam protection, and one researcher from the University of Linz in Austria responded although the survey was not disseminated at this University.

Figure 4.1 – Institutions in the dataset (N=716)

As Figure 4.2 shows, most of the survey respondents were researchers who have completed their doctoral degree; 73% have completed their PhD while 27% have not done so yet.

Figure 4.2 – PhD completed (N=716)

Figure 4.3 provides a more specific overview of the respondents' status and shows the distribution of respondents by career stage. Established and leading researchers comprised the largest shares of the researchers in the dataset with 36% and 27% respectively, while first stage researchers and recognized researchers comprised almost 20% and 18% of the data, respectively. Regarding the respondents' disciplines,

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several disciplines were represented in the dataset, although there is a strong bias towards the Natural Sciences.

Figure 4.3 – Respondents’ career stage (N=713)

As Figure 4.4 shows, over half of the survey respondents were from the Natural Sciences (53%). Engineering, Humanities, Medicine, and the Social Sciences comprised 9%-12% of the respondents. Researchers from the Agricultural Sciences were the least represented in the dataset (4.9%).

Figure 4.4 – Disciplines (N=710)

4.2 Survey results

This section displays the main results from the survey. We display the data, based largely on likert scales⁷, with stacked bar graphs. For visualization purposes, we excluded “don’t knows” from the likert plots. To display some of the variations and patterns in the data, we also drew on Principal Component Analysis (PCA) throughout the section and displayed the data using biplots. This approach allowed us to identify groups that are similar and the variables that distinguish groups from another. PCA aims at reducing the dimensionality of a multivariate data set while accounting for the variation in the data (Everitt and Hothorn, 2011). It transforms the dimensionality of the variables into a new set of variables (the principal components). Biplots are an ideal way to display the results of PCA. The distance between the points representing the units reflects the generalized distance between the units. The length of the vector from the origin to the coordinates representing a particular variable reflects the variance of that variable, and the correlation of two variables is reflected by the angle between the two corresponding vectors for the two variables. The smaller the angle, the greater the correlation (Everitt and Hothorn, 2011). For the biplots, we include the “don’t knows” since removing them could alter the results. Last, we draw on path analysis⁸ to understand how researchers’ attitudes lead to data reuse.

4.2.1 Respondents’ career motivations

In order to understand the goals that may influence researchers’ behavior and attitudes, Figure 4.5 displays the respondents’ career motivations. According to their responses, the quality and number of publications are the most important drivers of the researchers’ careers. Specifically, a share of 97% of the respondents considered the quality of publications to be either somewhat important, important, or very important. Similarly, a share of 96% considered the number of publications to be either somewhat important, important, or very important. According to the responses, data publication, societal outreach, and good teaching evaluations played a lesser role as career drivers. Figure 4.6 displays another visualization of this variable by discipline. Figure 4.6 conveys a biplot of career motivations by discipline. The figure shows that the number and quality of publications correlated highly. The other dimensions of career motivation are less correlated, i.e. teaching evaluations, societal outreach, and data publication. There is little variation among groups, though slight differences are visible.

⁷A likert scale is a 5 or 7-point scale used to measure respondents’ agreement with a given statement.

⁸Path analysis is type of statistical analysis used to evaluate patterns of effects within a set of variables. Here, we draw on path analysis to assess how individual attitudes affect data reuse.

Figure 4.5 – Respondents’ career motivations

Figure 4.6 – Respondents’ career motivations by discipline

Figure 4.6: The distance between the points reflects the generalized distance between the units. The length of the vector from the origin to the coordinates representing a particular variable reflects the variance of that variable, and the correlation of two variables is reflected by the angle between the two corresponding vectors for the two variables. The smaller the angle, the greater the correlation (Everitt and Hothorn, 2011).

4.2.2 Reuse and data sources

Regarding data (re)use, Figure 4.7 displays the frequency with which researchers (re)use different types of data. According to the survey responses, the two most used and reused types of data were numeric data and software developer tools. A share of 86% of the respondents claimed that numeric data use was either somewhat important, important, or very important. Conversely, 78% of the respondents claimed that software developer tool use was either somewhat important, important, or very important. Regarding data reuse, these two types of data ranked similar in their importance. Ninety percent of the respondents claimed that numeric data and software developer tools are somewhat important, important, or very important. The other types of data vary in their use and reuse. However, the number of respondents that answered each item also varies between the “use” and “reuse” items.

Figure 4.7 – Data use and reuse

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Figure 4.8 displays sources and tools that researchers claimed to use to search for data. The top three sources for data included supplementary data from publications, discipline-specific data repositories, and data from public sources. A share of 80% of respondents considered supplementary data from publications to be a somewhat important, important, or very important source of reusable data, while 77% and 73% considered discipline-specific repositories or data from public sources to be important, respectively. The three least-used data sources were commercial providers, websites of individual researchers, and catch-all repositories. Regarding tools, the top three included references to data in publications, search engines, and researchers' own academic network. A share of 93%, 92%, and 84% considered the latter to be important, respectively. Catch-all data repositories, and aggregated platforms were the least-used tools with 47% and 43% attributed importance, respectively.

Figure 4.8 – Importance of Sources and tools for finding data

Sources of reusable data

Tools for finding reusable data

4.2.3 Aspects that influence data reuse

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Figure 4.9 displays the main aspects that influence a researcher’s decision to reuse data and the criteria they should fulfill. The top three criteria that data should fulfill, according to the researchers’ perspective, encompassed the quality of the data, consistency and verification of the data, and the credibility of the research institution the data stems from. Regarding the FAIR aspects that influence data reuse, the top three criteria included data accessibility, availability, understandability, and the documentation quality.

Figure 4.9 – Aspects that influence data reuse

Aspects that influence reuse (data should ...)

FAIR aspects that influence reuse (data should ...)

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Figures 4.10 and 4.11 display the biplots of aspects that influence data reuse and FAIR aspects of data reuse. Figure 4.10 shows three main components. First, data should be 1) up-to-date, easily convertible, stem from a credible research institution and conform to a given format and be in a credible repository. Another main group includes that 2) the data should be consistent and verified, be of high quality, should have been used before, have been rarely used, be product of a credible researcher, be used in publications, and be used in high impact journals and publications. A last group includes that 3) data should have been published as a data paper, contain data in a standardized format, and have been digitized.

Figure 4.10 – Aspects that influence data reuse

Figure 4.10: The distance between the points reflects the generalized distance between the units. The length of the vector from the origin to the coordinates representing a particular variable reflects the variance of that variable, and the correlation of two variables is reflected by the angle between the two corresponding vectors for the two variables. The smaller the angle, the greater the correlation (Everitt and Hothorn, 2011).

Figure 4.11 shows that the groups revealed even less variation by groups than in figure 4.10. Here, the variables were less correlated with one another. At the top we see a few highly correlated variables: data should be accompanied by high quality documentation, data should be described in a standardized way, be easily accessible, provide terms of use, and data should include persistent identifiers and curated by professionals and accompanied by software/code. The rest of the variables were less

correlated with one another as the angles between the vectors show.

Figure 4.11 – FAIR aspects that influence data reuse

Figure 4.11: The distance between the points reflects the generalized distance between the units. The length of the vector from the origin to the coordinates representing a particular variable reflects the variance of that variable, and the correlation of two variables is reflected by the angle between the two corresponding vectors for the two variables. The smaller the angle, the greater the correlation (Everitt and Hothorn, 2011).

As mentioned in the literature review, while data sharing does not necessarily lead to reuse, these two concepts are inextricably linked. Before turning to data reuse, figure 4.12 displays the main reasons that researchers refrain from sharing data. One main component encompasses reasons related to third parties; third party consultation and whether the data belong to a third party. The remaining reasons are more related to each other and include fear of misinterpretation, the data not being of general interest, time reasons, data protection concerns, and the desire to analyze the data further.

Figure 4.12 – Respondents’ reasons not to share data

Figure 4.12: The distance between the points reflects the generalized distance between the units. The length of the vector from the origin to the coordinates representing a particular variable reflects the variance of that variable, and the correlation of two variables is reflected by the angle between the two corresponding vectors for the two variables. The smaller the angle, the greater the correlation (Everitt and Hothorn, 2011).

4.2.4 Importance of services

This section covers the main services that the researchers considered most important and their familiarity with EOSC and FAIR principles. Figure 4.13 shows that the three main services that are crucial to researchers include short-term and mid-term storage, long-term data repositories, and support for publishing data. Next we asked them to rank the importance on services that were not yet available. Here we found an overlap with the importance of overall services (whether they are available or not). The three most important services that were not yet available included: computing services, long-term data repositories, and virtual research environments.

Figure 4.13 – Importance of research services

Important services for research

Importance of additional services (not yet available)

Figure 4.14 displays the structure of the importance of not-yet-available services. We see that support with data management and support for publishing data are highly correlated. Next, we see that long term repositories and computing services also correlated with each other. Short-term storage is not closely correlated with any of the other variables, while another cluster is comprised of support with data protection, virtual research environments, support with property rights, and support with ethics requirements.

Figure 4.14 – Importance of services for research

4.2.5 Familiarity with EOSC and FAIR

Last, Figure 4.15 displays overall familiarity with EOSC and FAIR principles. EOSC is more widely unknown than FAIR principles with over 90% claiming they are unfamiliar with it. Regarding FAIR principles, researchers are more familiar with them compared to EOSC with 35% claiming they are familiar with them.

Figure 4.15 – Familiarity with EOSC and FAIR principles

4.2.6 How attitudes lead to data reuse

In this section we present the results of a path analysis to explain reuse based on acceptance, i.e. the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology model described in the [literature review](#) (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Path analysis provides the connections between sets of variables and is displayed in a path diagram. The first diagram in [Figure 16](#) is drawn before the analysis to represent the connections that we would expect based on the literature. The second path diagram in [Figure 17](#) represents the results of the statistical analysis and shows what was actually found in our data. Our guiding question for the analysis was: which attitudinal and behavioral factors lead to data reuse? We expand on the four explanatory factors of data reuse presented by Venkatesh et al. (2003): performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions. In line with this model, we integrated hedonic motivation as an additional acceptance factor to comprehensively capture the users’ individual characteristics (Reichenbach et al., 2020). We draw on this model using the attitudinal and behavioral questions from the survey. They are all measured on a scale from 1 (strongly disagree)–7 (strongly agree).

Performance expectancy is defined as the individuals’ perception that the examined behavior will increase his or her performance and is measured by: “Reusing data/material increases my chances of achieving research goals that are important to me” and “Reusing data/material will enable me to accomplish my research goals more quickly” . Social influence refers to the influence of the individuals’ social en-

environment and facilitating conditions are related to supportive terms for the (reuse) behavior (Venkatesh et al., 2003) and is measured by: “Other researchers, who are important to me, think that I should reuse data/material”. Hedonic motivation refers to the pleasure, specifically the flow experience of the individual (Runsten, 2019) and is measured by: “I like reusing data/material”. Facilitating conditions are measured by: “I have the necessary competences and means to reuse data/material”. Attitude is measured by the items RattitudeA-RattitudeD (whether reusing data is encouraged (A), supported (B), a common practice (C), and whether enough data is available(D)). Reuse intention is measured by: “I intend to reuse data in the future”, and reuse behavior is measured by the Rreusefreq questions (the frequency with which respondents reuse different types of data). Figure 4.16 shows the delineated model. We excluded effort expectancy from our analysis as it can not be investigated technology-independent.

Figure 4.16 – Data acceptance and reuse model

Source: Adapted based on Venkatesh et al. (2003, p. 448). Note: The model outlines the expected effects within the set of variables. The model can be read from left to right. For example, performance expectancy affects reuse intention and attitudes, which both influence reuse behavior.

The path coefficients are depicted in Table 4.2. Performance expectancy and hedonic motivation show significant positive effects on reuse intention, as well as significant indirect effects on reuse behavior. Moreover, attitude mediates the effects of facilitating conditions and social influence on reuse behavior. The analysis validates our data acceptance and reuse model outlined in Figure 16 in the empirical analysis based on Venkatesh et al. (2003) and Reichenbach et al. (2020). The results displayed in Figure 17 indicate that the acceptance and reuse of research data are directly driven by the users’ performance expectancy. These findings can be explained by the fact that time is a precious resource in the scientific context. Results are needed in ever shorter time intervals in order to keep up with the increasing dynamics in science and society (Warner and Wäger, 2019). Therefore, technology

services should focus on efficiency to promote the reuse of research data. Moreover, hedonistic motivation is an important direct driver of data reuse. Users anticipate the potential joy of reusing data and expect a flow experience from it (Runsten, 2019). In line with the literature, the attitude to reuse data has a mediating role in the effect of social influence and facilitating conditions on reuse behavior (Dwivedi et al., 1989). In other words, contextual acceptance factors, such as social influence and facilitating conditions, influence the users' attitude, which in turn motivates them to act. For example, if scientists from universities are encouraged to reuse data, their attitude towards data reuse will increase, and so will their actual reuse behavior. Therefore, research organizations should provide a supportive environment including for example leadership support and appropriate infrastructure, so that scientists can easily access and analyze data. However, as the reliability and validity were not fully supported, the results must be carefully judged.

Table 4.1 – Path analysis results

Path coefficients	Coef.	p-value
ATT → RB	0.213	0.001
RI → RB	0.111	0.036
FC → ATT	0.296	0.000
FC → RB	0.020	0.804
HM → ATT	0.031	0.643
HM → RI	0.535	0.000
PE → ATT	0.132	0.095
PE → RI	0.289	0.000
SI → ATT	0.270	0.000
SI → RI	0.081	0.072
Indirect effects		
FC → RB	0.063	0.004
HM → RB	0.066	0.036
PE → RB	0.060	0.026
SI → RB	0.066	0.006

Notes: ATT: Attitude; FC: Facilitating conditions; HM: Hedonic motivation; PE: Performance expectancy; RB: Reuse behavior; RI: Reuse intention; SI: Social influence.

This analysis is the first to investigate reuse of research data based on acceptance. A data acceptance and reuse model in Figure 16 is conceptualized based on the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (Venkatesh et al., 2003). The findings in Figure 17 indicate that in order to promote the reuse of data, individual and contextual acceptance factors of potential users are crucial. Given that the users'

Figure 4.17 – Results of the data acceptance and reuse analysis

Performance expectancy = “Reusing data/material increases my chances of achieving research goals that are important to me” and “Reusing data/material will enable me to accomplish my research goals more quickly” .

Social influence = “Other researchers, who are important to me, think that I should reuse data/material” .

Hedonic motivation = “I like reusing data/material” .

Facilitating conditions = “I have the necessary competences and means to reuse data/material” .

Attitude = whether reusing data is encouraged (A), supported (B), a common practice (C), or available(D).

Reuse intention = intention to reuse data in the future

Reuse behavior = the frequency with which respondents reuse different types of data.

performance is key, it is crucial that aspects such as the automation of repetitive tasks, convenient feedback functions, or adaptability of supportive technologies to individual needs be ensured. The flow experienced while reusing research data (i.e., hedonic motivation) should exceed the users’ expectations. Therefore, functional and joy-arousing technologies such as virtual realities should be provided. By enhancing teamwork and cross-functional or -organizational collaboration, it is also possible to increase the reuse of data. Moreover, facilitating conditions such as on-line tutorials, seminars, and training courses can foster the reuse of research data.

4.2.7 Survey results: Key Findings

Key Findings

- The top two types of **used** and **reused** data include numeric data and software developer tools. The remaining types of data vary in terms of their (re)use. We recommend focussing on an increased availability of data types that are not as common as the more often-reused data types.
- The main factors that determine data reusability included the quality of the data, consistency of the data, being a product of a credible research institution and credible researchers, and that data be published in a credible repository.
- Regarding FAIR aspects that influence data reusability, the researchers highlighted accessibility, understandability of the terms of use, and that data be accompanied by high-quality documentation, have persistent identifiers and be described in a standardized way.
- The main sources and tools for finding data were supplementary data from publications, discipline-specific repositories, data from public sources. Main tools were references to data in publications, search engines, and researchers' own academic network.
- The most important services for research mentioned by the researchers included short-term and mid-term storage, long-term data repositories, support for publishing data and computing services.
- The main services for research that are not yet available but considered most important include computing services, long-term data repositories, virtual research environments and support for publishing data.
- The findings of the path model indicate that performance expectancy determines acceptance and reuse of research data. To promote the reuse of data, individual and contextual acceptance factors of potential users are relevant. As the users' performance is important, automation of repetitive tasks, convenient feedback functions, or adaptability of supportive technologies to individual needs should be ensured.

5 Conclusion

This deliverable provided several areas of improvement and insights pertaining to the future of EOSC. The events organized provided key feedback based on the results of the survey. The feedback underscored the importance of three main aspects: communication, training, metadata standardization, and the role of hackathons as a useful tool to become acquainted and increase the reuse of the National Initiatives Survey. Experts emphasized that increased effort in motivating and supporting researchers is necessary to implement open science policies, e.g. by providing the necessary resources, clear guidelines, and rewards. They also underscored the importance of training at all levels, but also in local languages. This is especially important when we think of developing open science bottom-up rather than top-down in the future. The events showed that hands-on experiences such as hackathons can be a straight-forward way to promote the reuse of data while simultaneously providing users and potential users with knowledge of the data. While it was a closed event, trainings like this mini-hackathon may continue to play a crucial role in increasing researchers' familiarity and re(use) of the data.

The qualitative interviews highlighted several potential areas of improvement regarding the FAIRness of data. However, the needs vary widely by discipline and we interviewed a limited amount of researchers (14 total). This means that the interviews provide valuable insight, however the findings should also be treated with caution. Looking towards the future of EOSC regarding data [findability](#), the researchers suggest that there is room for improvement with existing repositories regarding their scope and searching mechanisms. The interviews also mentioned potential room for improvement regarding [accessability](#): facilitating access despite legal barriers and requiring high-quality metadata and documentation, which of course plays an important role for [interoperability](#). The interviews implied that investing more money into software development in order to integrate and consolidate the research landscape could lead to increase [data reuse](#), however the following aspects are key: quality of the data, role of good data documentation and metadata, source of the data, publication of the data, overall transparency by the data producers and reliability of the data, and relevance. Overall, the qualitative interviews pointed to several areas that could be improved to increase the FAIRization of workflows in the future. Many of these aspects are already work in progress and will most likely improve over time.

The survey provided an overview of how researchers go about reusing data, the importance of different resources, and how attitudes affect data reuse. The top two types of [data use and reuse](#) include numeric data and software developer tool reuse. The main factors behind data reuse [determining data reusability](#) included the quality of the data, consistency of the data, being product of a credible research institution and researchers, and being published in a credible repository. Regarding [FAIR aspects that influence data reusability](#), the researchers highlighted accessibility, understandability of the terms of use, high-quality documentation, and the use of persistent identifiers. The [findings of the path model](#) indicate that to promote the reuse of data, individual and contextual acceptance factors of potential users are relevant. As the users' performance is important, automation of repetitive tasks, convenient feedback functions, or adaptability of supportive technologies to individual needs should be ensured. Looking towards the future, EOSC will require some kind of bottom-up approach based on communication and training in local languages, and dissemination (by researchers) within researchers networks to make EOSC more engrained in the research culture.

While [the survey](#) provided important insight into reuse, it also faced several limitations. First, the survey was designed to target all researchers that were contacted and was conceptualized as a complete sample. However, given legal restrictions, we were unable to directly contact the researchers and send them reminders, thus hindering participation in the survey. The newsletter as a tool to contact researchers proved to be highly inadequate. The mailing lists and directly contacting researchers proved to be more effective, however, given the timing with the pandemic and overall survey fatigue, we did not come close to reaching a representative study. Surveys have overall suffered from declining response rates in recent years ([Beullens et al., 2018](#)). Non-response is a widespread problem and makes it more difficult to reach the target group, which can increase the sampling error. This can be attributed to the general trend of declining response rates and survey fatigue arising from the heightened number of online activities due to the COVID-19 Pandemic. There were overall difficulties in getting all targeted researchers to participate, but we also have varying patterns of response rates across items in the survey. For future studies, more time and resources should be channelled into survey design in order to reach more researchers and ensure their participation. Second, the response rate is extremely low compared to the number of researchers we targeted. For this reason, we were not able to analyze the data on a granular level (e.g. by comparing institutions or countries). The sample was thus not representative of the target population. In addition, our sample may be biased towards the natural sciences given that half of the respondents represented this discipline. Despite these limitations, we were still able to reach 592 researchers, which can still provide insight into several aspects of data (re)use and services.

However, the findings highlight several potential areas of improvement. Incentives and rewards for researchers are crucial in encouraging them to share and reuse data

in a way that benefits them. This implies, on the one hand, emphasizing the value of data publications, fostering the use of common and well-known licenses, and creating researcher network to increase awareness of EOSC and FAIR principles. On the other hand, the role of funding agencies in increasing data sharing – and thus an increasingly common practice – will play an important role in the future of open science. Data reuse should be promoted as an advantage for the researcher rather than an obligation. Since performance expectancy plays an important role, it is crucial that the quality of data and accompanying documentation improve, that data is made as easy to use as possible, and that the use of data papers is encouraged. Increasing acceptance of data reuse and FAIR practices is a long-term goal as change is likely to happen slowly. This process of change can be more easily facilitated by using these findings and similar endeavours.

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